

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29

Maternal immune protection against infectious diseases

Stephanie N. Langel^{1*}, Maria Blasi^{2,3} and Sallie R. Permar⁴

¹ Duke Center for Human Systems Immunology and Department of Surgery, Durham, NC, USA

² Duke Human Vaccine Institute, Duke University Medical Center, Durham, North Carolina, USA.

³ Department of Medicine, Division of Infectious Diseases, Duke University Medical Center, Durham, North Carolina, USA.

⁴ Department of Pediatrics, Weill Cornell Medicine, New York, New York, USA.

Address correspondence to:

Sallie R. Permar
Department of Pediatrics
525 East 68th Street, M-622
Box 225
New York, NY 10065
T: 212.746.4111
sallie.permar@med.cornell.edu

Declaration of interests: S.R.P provides consulting services to Moderna, Merck, Pfizer, Dynavax, and Hoopkia related to cytomegalovirus vaccines, and participates in a sponsored research programs with Merck and Moderna. The authors have declared that no conflict of interest exists.

30 **Abstract:**

31 The maternal immune system protects developing offspring against pathogens before
32 birth via transplacental transfer and after birth through secreted milk. This transferred
33 maternal immunity influences each generation's susceptibility to infections and
34 responsiveness to immunization. Thus, boosting immunity in the maternal-neonatal
35 dyad is a potentially valuable public health strategy. Additionally, at critical times during
36 fetal and postnatal development, environmental factors and immune stimuli influence
37 immune development. These 'windows of opportunity' offer a chance to identify both
38 risk and protective factors that promote long-term health and limit disease. Here, we
39 review pre- and postpartum maternal immune factors that protect against infectious
40 agents in offspring and how they may shape the infant's immune landscape over time.
41 Additionally, we discuss the influence of maternal immunity on responsiveness to
42 immunization in early life. Lastly, when maternal factors are insufficient to prevent
43 neonatal infectious disease, we discuss pre- and postnatal therapeutic strategies for the
44 maternal-neonatal dyad.

45

46 **Mechanisms of maternal immunity against infection: prepartum**

47 *Innate immune defenses at the maternal-fetal interface*

48 Innate immune defenses at the maternal-fetal interface play an integral role in restricting
49 vertical transmission of microorganisms and congenital infection in the fetus. This area
50 of immunobiology is rapidly evolving, and strategies to engage specialized innate cells
51 in immunotherapeutics are ongoing. There are multiple excellent recent reviews on
52 innate immune defenses at the maternal-fetal interface (Ander et al., 2019; Megli and

53 Coyne, 2022; Semmes and Coyne, 2021). Therefore, in this review, we will focus on
54 transferred humoral and cellular immunity that can be enhanced through vaccination or
55 engineered for passive administration, including transplacental and breast milk transfer
56 of maternal antibodies and immune cells. The role of other breastmilk
57 immunomodulators, such as glycans, cytokines, and antimicrobial proteins in protection
58 against infectious disease in offspring is also discussed.

59

60 *Mechanisms of transplacental transfer of maternal antibodies*

61 A major component of the infant's first defenses against the array of pathogens that
62 they can encounter is passively-transferred maternal antibodies. Circulating maternal
63 IgG antibodies traverse the placental cell layers to the fetal circulation via transcytosis
64 mediated by the neonatal Fc receptor (FcRn) expressed on the surface of
65 syncytiotrophoblasts (Simister, 2003) (Figure 1). While IgG is the dominant and possibly
66 only antibody isotype transferred across the human placenta, intriguingly, IgE has
67 recently been reported to cross the placenta in an FcRn-dependent fashion in mice and
68 associates with fetal mast cells to influence allergic responses (Msallam et al., 2020).
69 IgG subclass can impact IgG transfer efficiency and IgG1 dominates as the most
70 efficiently-transferred subclass followed by IgG3 and then IgG2 and IgG4 (Clements et
71 al., 2020). Although evidence suggests that passive transfer rates of IgG3, IgG4, and
72 IgG2 can be impacted by the mother's antibody repertoire, length of a term pregnancy,
73 and recent maternal vaccination (Clements et al., 2020; Schlaudecker et al., 2018).

74 Maternal hypergammaglobulinemia has been shown to impact placental IgG
75 transfer, partially explaining the reduced placental IgG transfer efficiency during

76 maternal human immunodeficiency virus (HIV-1), malaria, and cytomegalovirus (CMV)
77 infections (Atwell et al., 2016; de Moraes-Pinto et al., 1998; Semmes et al., 2021a),
78 indicating a potential FcRn saturation threshold and potential degradation of unbound
79 IgG. However, placental FcRn expression levels are reported as both associated
80 (Lozano et al., 2018) or not associated (Clements et al., 2020) with IgG transfer
81 efficiency, potentially due to differential FcRn expression at different placental sites of
82 collection and analysis. Recent work has examined whether there is selection of IgG
83 molecules beyond subclass for transfer across the placental barrier and whether
84 interactions with noncanonical Fc receptors present in placental cell layers, including Fc
85 gamma receptor (Fc γ R) I on Hoffbauer cells, Fc γ RIIb on fetal endothelium, and
86 Fc γ RIIIa, contribute to the selection of IgG for transfer to the fetal circulation (Jennewein
87 et al., 2019; Martinez et al., 2019). The selection of IgG subpopulations may be
88 influenced by Fc region characteristics, including placental noncanonical Fc receptor
89 binding and glycosylation (Jennewein et al., 2019; Martinez et al., 2019) however
90 contradictory evidence exists (Borghini et al., 2020). Antibody subclass and glycosylation
91 profiles may also impact maternal antibody half-life in the infant blood postpartum,
92 which can range from 28 to 35 days depending on antibody specificity (Oguti et al.,
93 2022) but in certain cases, like after maternal vaccination, can be extended up to 6
94 months or more (Shook et al., 2022).

95 These factors would subsequently impact isotype-specific neutralizing and non-
96 neutralizing Fc-mediated antibody effector functions in the neonate. Non-neutralizing
97 antibody functions include antibody-dependent cellular phagocytosis (ADCP), antibody-
98 dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity (ADCC), antibody-dependent complement

99 deposition (ADCD), and mast cell activation by IgE (Figure 1). These are induced when
100 the Fc antibody domain binds to complement proteins or FcγRs on innate effector cells
101 (Bournazos et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2018). While a detailed discussion of isotype-specific
102 interactions with FcγRs on innate immune cells is outside the scope of this review, it is
103 worth noting that IgG3 enhances neutralization potency and Fc effector function against
104 multiple infectious diseases (Kallolimath et al., 2021; Richardson et al., 2019) and
105 increased transplacental transfer of malaria-specific IgG3 is strongly associated with
106 reduced risk of clinical malaria during infancy (Dechavanne et al., 2017).

107 Maternal antibodies can also impact the ability of neonates to mount an immune
108 response, referred to as maternal antibody interference (Otero et al., 2020). While the
109 mechanisms are unclear, recent work demonstrated that maternal antibodies do not
110 impact germinal center formation or prevent B cell activation but limit plasma cell and
111 memory B cell differentiation in a titer-dependent manner (Vono et al., 2019). Other
112 hypothesized mechanisms of maternal antibody interference include vaccine antigen
113 removal via antibody-mediated phagocytosis and neutralization, epitope masking, and
114 cross-linking between the tyrosine-based activation motif of the B cell antigen receptor
115 and the tyrosine-based inhibitory motif of FcγRIIB, leading to antigen-specific B cell
116 inhibition (Niewiesk, 2014). Future efforts of precision-informed maternal immunization
117 strategies should take into consideration how the antigen, adjuvant, and stage of
118 gestation impact IgG subclass transfer ratios, glycosylation, Fc receptor affinity, half-life,
119 and maternal antibody interference.

120

121 *Impact of placentally-transferred antibodies against neonatal pathogens of global*
122 *importance*

123 The importance of placentally-transferred maternal antibodies is well established
124 (Fouda et al., 2018) and maternal antibody levels are correlated to neonatal protection
125 against viruses and bacteria. In an impressive study of 32 preterm and 46 term mother-
126 child dyads, Pou and colleagues probed the global repertoire of maternal IgG in the
127 blood of Swedish neonates by assessing antibodies against 93,904 epitopes from 206
128 viruses. The most common targeted viruses in maternal-newborn dyads were
129 adenovirus C, CMV, Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), Herpes simplex virus 1 (HSV-1), and
130 rhinovirus A (Pou et al., 2019). Interestingly, both term and preterm babies show similar
131 maternal IgG repertoires, irrespective of gestational age at birth, suggesting that titers of
132 maternal antibodies transferred but not diversity of the IgG repertoire increases the risk
133 of infection in preterm babies.

134 In the setting of mother-to-child transmission (MTCT), viral transmission to
135 infants occurs in the presence of antibodies that co-evolved with the transmitted virus.
136 For HIV-1, prior to the development of treatment, less than half of mothers would
137 transmit the virus to their infant despite many months of virus exposure (Taha, 2011),
138 suggesting a protective role for maternal immunity. An association between the
139 magnitude of maternal HIV-1 envelope (Env)-specific antibody responses and reduced
140 risk of MTCT has been reported (Bongertz et al., 2002; Permar et al., 2015), though not
141 universally observed (Mutucumarana et al., 2017; Zolla-Pazner et al., 2016). Moreover,
142 a genetic bottleneck exists in transmitted virus selection, as only one or a small number
143 of variants initiate infection in infants (Fouda et al., 2013b; Russell et al., 2013; Zhang et

144 al., 2010). While viral variants transmitted to infants have been reported as resistant to
145 neutralization by maternal plasma (Wu et al., 2006), other studies failed to replicate
146 these observations (Fouda et al., 2013b; Russell et al., 2011). One study implicated that
147 HIV-transmitting mothers had more broadly neutralizing antibody (bnAb) activity than
148 non-transmitting women (Ghulam-Smith et al., 2017). This phenomenon could be
149 explained by the observation that among HIV-infected women who have plasma bnAb
150 activity, bnAb-resistant variants circulating in their blood may be selected as infant
151 transmitted/founder variants (Martinez et al., 2020; Tu et al., 2022). Indeed, transmitting
152 mothers carry mutations in their circulating viral population that are associated with
153 bnAb escape (Kumar et al., 2021), indicating that bnAb escape variants have a
154 propensity for vertical transmission. An association of pre-existing infant ADCC with
155 reduced HIV-1 acquisition and lower morbidity has also been reported (Thomas et al.,
156 2021), supporting the role of Fc-mediated effector antibodies in modifying infant HIV
157 acquisition risk and outcome.

158 The most common congenital infection, human CMV, can have devastating
159 consequences for the neonate including growth and development abnormalities such as
160 microcephaly, hepatosplenomegaly, chorioretinitis, and sensorineural hearing loss
161 (Goderis et al., 2014). Interestingly, vertical transmission of both primary and
162 nonprimary congenital CMV (cCMV) can occur, demonstrating only a partially protective
163 effect of natural maternal immunity. In fact, higher neutralizing antibody responses have
164 been reported in transmitting mothers compared with non-transmitting mothers
165 (Dorfman et al., 2021; Semmes et al., 2021b) despite similar rates and magnitude of
166 maternal viremia (Semmes et al., 2021b). Interestingly, recent work has demonstrated

167 that non-neutralizing Fc effector-mediated antibody functions, such as ADCP are
168 important in reducing placental transmission of this highly cell-associated virus
169 (Semmes et al., 2021b). Additional data suggests that maternal effector cells, including
170 NK cells, may play a central role in viral clearance (Tabata et al., 2019).

171 Zika virus (ZIKV) is a recently emerged congenital pathogen identified in the
172 2015-2016 global outbreak that can result in microcephaly and neurodevelopmental
173 impairment in infants, known as congenital Zika syndrome (CZS) (Rasmussen et al.,
174 2016). Antibody enhancement of virus infection has also been associated with the risk
175 of infant CZS, indicating that the pre-existing maternal antibody responses or early
176 responses to infection could contribute to ZIKV congenital transmission (Robbiani et al.,
177 2019). Recent work has also highlighted the potential role of plasma IgM responses in
178 viral neutralization, as an ultrapotent neutralizing IgM antibody has been isolated from a
179 ZIKV-infected pregnant woman who delivered a healthy baby despite prolonged
180 maternal viremia (Singh et al., 2021).

181 Infants are typically at risk of severe disease and hospitalization from respiratory
182 viruses such as influenza and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), in the first months and
183 years of life. Fortunately, both placentally-transferred IgG and breastfeeding modify this
184 disease risk, demonstrating the major role of passive maternal antibodies in protecting
185 infants against viruses that infect the respiratory tract postnatally. High cord blood anti-
186 influenza A IgG levels were associated with a significantly reduced risk for respiratory
187 tract infections during the first six months of life (Albrecht et al., 2021). Further, the
188 severity of pneumonia caused by RSV was inversely related to level of neutralizing
189 antibodies (Lamprecht et al., 1976) and maternally-derived RSV neutralizing

190 antibodies in cord blood have been associated with a decreased risk of RSV
191 hospitalization in healthy infants below 6 months of age, and among infants age 6 to 11
192 months with recurrent wheeze (Stensballe et al., 2009).

193 Finally, it is not only the risk of virus infection in neonates that is modulated by
194 maternal antibodies. There is emerging evidence that anti-malarial antibodies in infants
195 can modulate disease risk, as high cord-blood anti-PfSEA (Plasmodium falciparum
196 schizont egress antigen)-1 antibody levels had 51.4% fewer cases of severe malarial
197 disease compared to children with lower anti-PfSEA-1 levels over 12 months of follow-
198 up (Kurtis et al., 2019).

199

200 *Vertically transferred maternal cells during pregnancy*

201 It is now well established that maternal immune cells transferred to the developing fetus
202 during pregnancy, impact the developing immune response of the fetus and neonate,
203 and persist for decades after birth (Kinder et al., 2017). Maternal microchimeric cells
204 (MMc) can be detected in cord blood (Hall et al., 1995) and fetal organs including
205 primary and secondary lymphoid tissues (Jonsson et al., 2008; Mold et al., 2008). MMc
206 have been identified as naïve and memory T cells, B cells, NK cells, and monocytes,
207 although they are disproportionately dominated by T cells (Kanaan et al., 2017; Mold et
208 al., 2008) yet their mechanism of transfer to the fetus is unclear (**Figure 1**). Kinder and
209 colleagues demonstrated that MMc play a specific role in promoting reproductive fitness
210 and the success of future pregnancies in mice by promoting tolerance to non-inherited
211 antigens expressed by MMc (Kinder et al., 2015).

212 However, what is known about the antimicrobial functions of MMc in human
213 offspring is sparse. In a recent study, neonatal mice with reduced levels of MMc
214 exhibited increased susceptibility to murine CMV which was mitigated after restoring
215 MMc (Stelzer et al., 2021). The authors also assessed the relationship between MMc in
216 human cord blood and the risk of respiratory infections (influenza-like illness, bronchitis,
217 tonsillitis, laryngotracheobronchitis) during 7-12 months of life, a time when maternal
218 antibodies have waned. Interestingly, there was an association between cord blood
219 MMc and the onset of respiratory infection that was significant in boys, but not girls,
220 demonstrating sex-specific influences of MMc (Stelzer et al., 2021). In human infants
221 with severe combined immunodeficiency, a substantial expansion of circulating
222 maternal T cells promoted host defenses against EBV (Touzot et al., 2012).
223 Interestingly, MMc was associated with increased *Plasmodium falciparum* infection in
224 children however decreased the risk of symptomatic malaria and malaria hospitalization
225 (Harrington et al., 2017), highlighting the importance of dissecting cellular specificities
226 and whether they directly or indirectly coordinate anti-malarial immune responses.
227 Further, infant birth MMc was associated with increased polyfunctional T cells to BCG
228 vaccination in early infancy (Balle et al., 2022). Future studies should focus on
229 elucidating the role of MMc in prevention of infection and response to immunization to
230 understand short and long-term impacts of MMc on neonatal health.

231

232 **Mechanisms of maternal immunity against infection: postpartum**

233 *Breast milk antibody passive transfer*

234 Breast milk extends the maternal immune influence into the postnatal period. The most
235 well-studied immunological component in breast milk are antibodies. The concentration
236 and proportion of antibodies change over the course of lactation from colostrum in the
237 first 48 hours of lactation to more mature milk by 10-15 days postpartum. Despite
238 variation between lactating mothers, IgA consistently dominates over IgG and IgM in
239 both colostrum and mature milk (Akhter et al., 2021; Hurley and Theil, 2011).
240 Additionally, multiple studies have demonstrated that IgA, IgG and IgM concentrations
241 are all significantly higher in colostrum compared to mature milk (Akhter et al., 2021).
242 Interestingly, in studies of prolonged lactation, a significant increase in secretory IgA
243 (sIgA) and IgG was observed during the second year of lactation (Czosnykowska-
244 Łukacka et al., 2020; Perrin et al., 2017). A variety of antibody subclasses are also
245 present in both colostrum and milk at different proportions. IgA2 is dominant over IgA1
246 (Sánchez-Salguero et al., 2019; Trégoat et al., 2001) and IgG1 is dominant over IgG2,
247 IgG3 and IgG4 (Mehta et al., 1989; Price et al., 1987).

248 Antibodies are transported to the mammary gland alveolae via isotype-
249 dependent mechanisms. For example, similar to placental transfer, circulating IgG is
250 transported by binding the IgG Fc portion to FcRn on the basolateral surface of
251 mammary gland epithelial cells (**Figure 2**), yet with lower efficiency as IgG levels in milk
252 are only about 10% of that in plasma. Subsequently, the receptor-bound IgG is
253 endocytosed and transported to the mammary gland alveolae (Cianga et al., 1999; Lu et
254 al., 2007). Breast milk IgA antibodies are derived from local antibody secreting cells
255 (ASCs) that migrate to the mammary gland mostly from the gut (Morteau et al., 2008;
256 Wilson and Butcher, 2004). Indeed, the IgA plasma cell repertoire in the mammary

257 gland is comprised of highly mutated sequences that largely mirrors that of the gut and
258 there are more clonally related sequences in the mammary gland and small intestine
259 compared to the mammary gland and colon (Lindner et al., 2015). Early animal studies
260 demonstrated that during late pregnancy and lactation, ASCs from the maternal gut
261 traffic to the mammary gland via the gut-mammary axis (Bohl et al., 1972; Roux et al.,
262 1977). Additionally, pregnancy-associated and mammogenic hormones also play a key
263 role in ASC trafficking to the mammary gland (Weisz-Carrington et al., 1978).

264 The transport of IgA and IgM from local ASCs in the mammary gland into milk is
265 mediated by polymeric Ig receptor (pIgR) on mammary gland epithelial cells. IgA or IgM
266 bind the J-chain peptide of pIgR and are endocytosed into the cell. IgA and IgM are
267 transported from the basolateral to the apical surface of the mammary gland epithelial
268 cell and released into the mammary alveolae producing sIgA and sIgM (Braathen et al.,
269 2002; Johansen and Kaetzel, 2011) (**Figure 2**). Indeed, the transport of sIgA and
270 therefore its concentration in mammary gland secretions mirrors the expression of pIgR
271 during lactation in animal models (De Groot et al., 2000). The contributions of non-
272 canonical Fc receptors, like FcγRI-III (Martinez et al., 2018), in transport of IgG, IgA or
273 IgM into mammary gland secretions is currently unknown.

274

275 *Lymphocytes in breast milk*

276 One understudied area of human milk immunity is the cellular component. Milk contains
277 approximately 10^2 to 10^5 viable leukocytes/mL that vary based on stage of lactation,
278 maternal and infant infection status, and individual variation (Hassiotou et al., 2013a;
279 Hassiotou et al., 2013b). Breast milk microchimerism of leukocytes and its impact on

280 neonatal immune status has been demonstrated in animal models (Darby et al., 2019;
281 Langel et al., 2015; Tuboly et al., 1995), however human milk maternal microchimerism
282 has not yet been conclusively demonstrated. Although, a recent report found that
283 maternal microchimerism increased up to three months of age and was positively
284 correlated with breastfeeding, suggesting the potential for human milk-derived maternal
285 microchimerism (Balle et al., 2021).

286

287 *B and T cells*

288 In addition to ASCs, breast milk is also enriched in memory B cells distinct from those in
289 circulation that express mucosal adhesion markers like $\alpha_4\beta_7$, $\alpha_4\beta_1$ and CD44 (Sacha et
290 al., 2015; Tuaille et al., 2009). However, the mechanisms of memory B cell enrichment
291 of breast milk B cells and whether the mammary gland maintains a resident pool of
292 memory B cells is unknown. Of the viable leukocytes in breast milk, 5-10% are T cells
293 which are also distinct from those found in blood (Hassiotou et al., 2013a). For example,
294 breast milk is enriched in effector memory populations and, similar to milk B cells, are
295 highly expressing mucosal homing markers (Kourtis et al., 2007; Sabbaj et al., 2005).
296 CMV (Moylan et al., 2017), EBV (Sabbaj et al., 2005), HIV (Sabbaj et al., 2002) and
297 influenza-specific (Ruben et al., 1982) T cells are detected in breast milk, are at higher
298 frequencies than in peripheral blood, and expand during maternal or infant infection
299 (Hassiotou et al., 2013a; Hassiotou et al., 2013b). In a recent report authors found
300 spike-specific T cells after SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccination in lactating mothers
301 (Armistead et al., 2021). These T cells were uniformly effector memory T cells and
302 expressed increased levels of mucosal homing markers CCR9 and CD103 when

303 compared to circulating T cells. Interestingly, the expression of CCR9 increased in
304 relation to time since delivery and time since 2nd vaccine dose further supporting that
305 the mammary gland is a mucosal site where local T cells are stimulated and mature
306 overtime (Armistead et al., 2021).

307

308 *Other human milk components*

309 Human milk oligosaccharides (HMOs) are multifunctional, unconjugated glycans that
310 are highly abundant and unique to human milk. HMOs play a significant role in
311 preventing infections by acting as soluble decoy receptors and blocking viral and
312 bacterial binding to host cells. For example, *Campylobacter jejuni* binds
313 fucosylsaccharides of human milk and other fucosyl alpha1,2-linked molecules that
314 blocks binding to mouse pup intestines in vivo and human intestinal mucosal ex vivo
315 (Ruiz-Palacios et al., 2003). Noroviruses bind histo blood group antigens (HBGAs)
316 which are structurally similar to HMOs and therefore HMOs can compete with HBGA
317 binding sites on norovirus capsid (Schroten et al., 2016; Weichert et al., 2016). HMOs
318 can also reduce the infectivity of G1P[8] and G2P[4] rotaviruses in vitro (Laucirica et al.,
319 2017) and porcine rotavirus infection in neonatal piglets (Hester et al., 2013). However,
320 interestingly in a later report HMOs were shown to enhance neonatal G10P rotavirus
321 infectivity in vitro and in vivo (Ramani et al., 2018). This suggests that rotaviruses that
322 infect neonates may have evolved mechanisms that utilize HMOs to increase infectivity,
323 promoting viral replication and transmission. This highlights the importance for using
324 relevant strains and utilizing clinical samples to validate host factors identified in vitro.

325 Additionally, pro- and anti-inflammatory and T-helper cell type (Th) 1, Th2 and T
326 regulatory cytokines have been discovered in colostrum and milk (Garofalo, 2010). The
327 most well studied, TGF- β downregulates intestinal bacterial-induced proinflammatory
328 responses in intestinal epithelial cells, promoting commensal bacterial colonization and
329 homeostasis (Haller et al., 2003; Konkel and Chen, 2011; Sitarik et al., 2017). High
330 concentrations of TGF- β in colostrum and milk may protect suckling neonates from
331 colonization by pathogenic bacteria like group B Streptococcus (Le Doare et al., 2017).
332 Furthermore, TGF- β in mammary gland secretions may promote IgA class-switching in
333 the suckling the neonatal intestine (Cerutti, 2008) as TGF- β -receptor-deficient mice
334 have severely impaired systemic and intestinal IgA responses (Cazac and Roes, 2000).

335 There are other components of human milk that modulate infant immune
336 response and protection against infection. These include antimicrobial proteins like
337 lactoferrin, lysozyme and α - β - defensins (Battersby et al., 2016), antiviral proteins like
338 tenascin-C (Fouda et al., 2013a), cargo-carrying extracellular vesicles (van Herwijnen et
339 al., 2018), and likely thousands more (Figure 2). This rapidly evolving field of breast milk
340 immunomodulators will lead to additional insights and strategies to boost neonatal
341 immunity and promote long-term immune regulation and health.

342

343 *Role of breast milk-transferred antibodies against neonatal pathogens*

344 Exclusive human milk feeding is associated with a decreased risk of diarrhea incidence,
345 duration and hospitalization. Specifically, increased levels of IgA antibodies in breast
346 milk correlate to protection against multiple diarrheal diseases, such as *Entamoeba*
347 *histolytica* and *Cryptosporidium* (Korpe et al., 2013). Additionally, breastfeeding has

348 also been associated with lower rotavirus shedding and IgA seroconversion after
349 immunization (Bautista-Marquez et al., 2016). Multiple studies in animal models have
350 demonstrated neonatal protection against pathogens like *S. typhimurium* (Shope and
351 Schiemann, 1991), *C. rodentium* (Caballero-Flores et al., 2019), and influenza (Sweet et
352 al., 1987) when cross-fostered to immunized mothers. In humans, one report suggests
353 that colostrum antibodies pass through the intestine into circulation for up to 72 hours
354 postpartum (Ogra et al., 1977) although more research is needed.

355 Necrotizing enterocolitis (NEC) is a devastating and the most common disease of
356 preterm infants causing inflammation and damage to the intestinal tissue resulting in
357 high morbidity and mortality and challenging sequelae in surviving infants including
358 failure to thrive and neurodevelopmental delays. NEC is associated with dysbiosis of the
359 gut microbiome characterized by increased *Proteobacteria*, increased
360 *Enterobacteriaceae*, and decreased *Firmicutes* and *Bacteroidetes* (Pammi et al., 2017). It
361 is well appreciated that breast milk reduces risk of NEC (Lucas and Cole, 1990).
362 Recently, IgA-bound bacteria in pre-term stool was associated with a decrease in NEC.
363 The bound bacteria were predominantly *Enterobacteriaceae* suggesting that IgA binding
364 helps prevent *Enterobacteriaceae*-induced inflammation in the preterm infant intestine.
365 Additionally, in the same study, mouse pups reared from IgA-deficient dams were more
366 likely to exhibit intestinal damage upon exposure to *Enterobacter* spp. and had higher
367 mortality (Gopalakrishna et al., 2019). Interestingly, previous efforts to prevent NEC with
368 intravenous immunoglobulins were unsuccessful (Eibl et al., 1988; Foster et al., 2016).
369 However, the antibodies in these studies were not targeted for specific bacteria and

370 they were monomeric IgA. Future studies should include recombinant bacteria-specific
371 dimeric IgA antibodies delivered intravenously or sIgA antibodies delivered orally.

372 Studies have demonstrated a benefit of exclusive breastfeeding on reduction of
373 morbidity and mortality associated with respiratory infections. For example, greater
374 exclusivity of breastfeeding in the first 6 months of life significantly decreased
375 respiratory illness in infants of mothers who had received the influenza vaccine in the
376 third trimester but not in infants of pneumococcal-vaccinated mothers (Schlaudecker et
377 al., 2013), likely due to passive transfer of influenza-specific IgA antibodies in breast
378 milk. A recent study found that levels of IgG against the prefusion RSV fusion
379 protein (pre-F) in BM was correlated with a decreased risk of RSV-induced acute
380 respiratory infection in breastfed infants (Mazur et al., 2019). However, this study did not
381 measure pre-F antibodies in serum of all mothers or in cord blood. Without accounting
382 for transplacental transfer of anti-preF IgG antibodies as a confounding factor, it is
383 difficult to interpret this study. Recently, multiple studies have demonstrated that SARS-
384 CoV-2-specific antibodies cross into breast milk after both infection and immunization
385 but not studies yet looking at levels of BM antibodies and protection against SARS-CoV-
386 2 infection and symptomatic COVID-19.

387

388 **Enhancing maternal protection to infants via vaccination**

389 *Active immunization strategies*

390 Maternal immunization during pregnancy offers the advantage of endowing the fetus
391 with maternal antibodies against infectious diseases prior to delivery. Vaccinations
392 during pregnancy are currently limited to tetanus, pertussis, and diphtheria (Tdap), and

393 the seasonal influenza vaccine. In general, inactivated vaccines are considered safe for
394 pregnant women and their fetuses (Sukumaran et al., 2015), whereas live vaccines are
395 not recommended due to theoretical potential risks to the fetus. The benefit of
396 immunization of tetanus toxoid during pregnancy on prevention of neonatal tetanus is
397 well established (Demicheli et al., 2015). Indeed since 1989, the World Health Assembly
398 has endorsed a global initiative to eliminate neonatal tetanus with the current goal of
399 vaccination at least 80% of pregnant women with at least two doses of a tetanus toxoid-
400 containing vaccine (WHO, 2020). Immunizing against pertussis and diphtheria during
401 pregnancy has also demonstrated protection against disease in neonates. For example,
402 maternal vaccine effectiveness against pertussis in infants ranged from 69-91% for
403 pertussis prevention, 91-94% for hospitalization prevention and 95% for prevention of
404 death due to pertussis (Vygen-Bonnet et al., 2020). Additionally, the trivalent inactivated
405 influenza vaccination during pregnancy is associated with reduction of influenza
406 infection in mothers and their infants younger than 6 months and decreased influenza-
407 related hospitalizations (Madhi et al., 2014; Tapia et al., 2016). Below we will focus on
408 vaccines for maternal immunization against other common neonatal pathogens,
409 including RSV, ZIKV, and CMV that are currently under development to protect infants
410 against serious sequelae of infection (**Figure 3**).

411

412 • RSV

413 RSV is the leading cause of pneumonia and bronchiolitis in infants, causing more than 3
414 million hospitalizations and over 50,000 deaths every year (Shi et al., 2017). Most RSV-
415 related deaths occur in low-income countries in children under six months of age, the

416 time when maternal passively-transferred immunity is waning. Increasing levels of
417 maternal antibodies against RSV could therefore protect infants during this critical
418 window of susceptibility to severe RSV infection. Active and passive immunizations are
419 currently the two main approaches to prevent RSV disease.

420 An RSV F glycoprotein nanoparticle vaccine was administered to 3051 pregnant
421 women to evaluate safety, immunogenicity, and vaccine efficacy against RSV-
422 associated lower respiratory tract infection in their infants through the first 90 and 180
423 days of life (Madhi et al., 2020). Although the primary endpoint for vaccine efficacy was
424 not met, the results of the trial with respect to the other end points of RSV-associated
425 and all-cause respiratory disease in infants suggested potential benefits of maternal
426 RSV vaccination. Improved understanding of the RSV F protein and the introduction of
427 pre-F stabilizing mutations (McLellan et al., 2013; Swanson et al., 2011), which are
428 advantageous for the induction of potent neutralizing antibodies, have enabled rapid
429 advances in RSV vaccine development. There are currently two maternal vaccines in
430 phase 3 trials (NCT04424316, NCT04605159), both using pre-fusion F subunit
431 vaccines.

432

433 • CMV

434 The ability of human herpesviruses to modulate and evade the host immune response
435 makes vaccine development particularly challenging. cCMV infection can be due to
436 primary infection of the mother during pregnancy, reactivation of CMV from latency and
437 subsequent in utero transmission or following reinfection with a different CMV strain.
438 Maternal vaccination is therefore an attractive strategy to prevent cCMV and a modeling

439 study predicted that vaccination of women of reproductive age can yield substantial
440 reductions of cCMV in 20 years (31.7–71.4% if 70% of women are effectively
441 vaccinated) (Rozhnova et al., 2020). The most successful CMV vaccine tested clinically
442 to date is a recombinant CMV Envelope glycoprotein B with MF59 adjuvant given at 0,
443 1, and 6 months to CMV-seronegative women within 1 year after they had given birth
444 demonstrated 50% efficacy at preventing CMV infection in this population (Pass et al.,
445 2009). Further, one cCMV infection was detected among 81 infants born to mothers in
446 the vaccine group, and three infections among 97 infants born to mothers in the placebo
447 group, indicating its potential in also reducing cCMV transmission.

448 Several other vaccine strategies based on proteins, peptides, virus like particles
449 (VLP) and DNA have been evaluated in phase 1 and 2 clinical trials (reviewed in (Inoue
450 et al., 2018), and more recently an mRNA based vaccine (mRNA-1647) has advanced
451 to phase 3 trial (NCT05085366) to evaluate the prevention of primary CMV infection in
452 seronegative women ages 16-40 years. mRNA-1647 is a vaccine combining six
453 mRNAs: five mRNAs encoding the subunits that form the CMV membrane-bound
454 pentamer complex, an entry complex for epithelial and endothelial cells, and one mRNA
455 encoding the full-length membrane-bound glycoprotein B (gB) (John et al., 2018). Data
456 released from the Phase 2 study of mRNA-1647 demonstrated that in vaccinated CMV
457 seronegative participants neutralizing antibody titers against epithelial cell infection were
458 at least 20-fold higher than titers of a CMV seropositive group, while no difference in
459 neutralizing antibody titers against fibroblast infection was observed.

460

461 • HIV

462 Antiretroviral therapy (ART) of HIV-infected women has resulted in reduced burden of
463 pediatric HIV-infection: however, the prevalence of maternal HIV infection remains high
464 in sub-Saharan African countries. A maternal HIV vaccine that synergizes with maternal
465 ART could further reduce infant HIV infections. However, developing a vaccine against
466 HIV has proven particularly challenging. Most HIV vaccine trials to date, including those
467 conducted in pregnant women (Hompe et al., 2020; Wright et al., 1999) used the HIV
468 Envelope (Env) immunogen, which is comprised of the gp160 glycoprotein that is
469 cleaved to yield gp120 and gp41. These strategies focused on variable region peptides,
470 recombinant gp120 proteins, and uncleaved gp140 or gp160 Envs (Sliepen and
471 Sanders, 2016) which elicited neutralizing antibody (nAb) responses against easy-to-
472 neutralize HIV-1 strains (tier 1 viruses) and rarely against more neutralization-resistant
473 circulating HIV-1 strains (tier 2 viruses) (van Schooten and van Gils, 2018). These Env
474 immunogens are poor mimics of the native, fusion-competent conformation of Env on
475 virions (Ringe et al., 2013), which likely precluded the elicitation of Abs to
476 conformationally conserved neutralizing epitopes (Kwong et al., 2002). Passive
477 immunotherapy with bnAbs has proven effective in preventing simian-human
478 immunodeficiency virus (SHIV) infection in nonhuman primates (NHPs) (Gautam et al.,
479 2016; Shingai et al., 2013). In the context of vaccination, nAb titers against the infecting
480 virus have correlated with protection (Pauthner et al., 2019). Thus, eliciting bnAbs is
481 thought to be required for a protective vaccine against HIV-1 infection in humans.
482 Recent HIV-1 vaccine efforts have led to the development of conformationally stabilized
483 Env trimer immunogens that have consistently induced autologous tier 2 nAb responses
484 in rabbits and macaques (de Taeye et al., 2015; Sanders et al., 2015). Some of these

485 Env trimers are currently being evaluated in clinical trials in adults 18-55 years of age
486 (NCT04915768, NCT05217641). Yet, bnAb responses are also reported to be elevated
487 in transmitting mothers, a phenomenon that may be tied to transmission of bnAb-
488 escape variants, as described above. Several MTCT studies have suggested that
489 antibody dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC) as well as other antibody functionalities
490 may limit HIV acquisition (Mabuka et al., 2012; Milligan et al., 2015), suggesting that in
491 addition to inducing bnAbs, a maternal HIV vaccine enhancing antibody effector
492 functions could help prevent MTCT.

493

494 • Influenza virus

495 Influenza infection is an important cause of morbidity in infants (El Guerche-Seblain et
496 al., 2019) and pregnant women are more vulnerable to serious sequelae of influenza
497 virus infections (Rasmussen et al., 2012). Specifically, influenza infection during
498 pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of preterm birth, low infant birthweight
499 and both neonatal and maternal admission to the intensive care unit (ICU) (Doyle et al.,
500 2013). For these reasons, influenza vaccination during pregnancy became part of the
501 World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations in 2012 (2012). Influenza
502 vaccination during pregnancy decreases rates of respiratory illness in both the mother
503 and the infant (Dabrera et al., 2014; Jarvis et al., 2020) with efficacy rates between 31
504 and 70% for the mothers and between 30 and 63% for the infants (Omer, 2017).
505 Influenza vaccination during pregnancy increases vaccine-specific antibody titers in the
506 cord blood that persist in the neonate for at least 2 months (Zhong et al., 2019).
507 Neutralizing antibody titers are the main correlate of vaccine induced protection against

508 influenza infection (Ohmit et al., 2011), but other antibody effector functions might also
509 play a role (Boudreau and Alter, 2019). Profiling of influenza-specific antibody subclass
510 levels, Fcγ receptor (FCGR) binding levels, and antibody-dependent innate immune
511 functions in a clinical trial of maternal influenza vaccination, demonstrated that selective
512 transfer of FCGR-binding antibodies contributes to infant protection against influenza
513 infection (Boudreau et al., 2022).

514

515 • Zika virus (ZIKV)

516 Various ZIKV vaccines have been developed and tested to control future epidemics and
517 to prevent congenital syndrome. These include inactivated, DNA- and mRNA-based
518 vaccines which have entered phase I/II clinical trials in healthy adults (Gaudinski et al.,
519 2018; Modjarrad et al., 2018). Evidence that a maternal vaccine against ZIKV infection
520 can protect infants from congenital disease come from studies in pregnant mice
521 vaccinated with a live-attenuated (LAV) ZIKV vaccine (Shan et al., 2019) and non-
522 human primates (NHPs) vaccinated with a DNA-based ZIKV vaccine (Van Rompay et
523 al., 2019). Immunization of pregnant mice with LAV did not cause any adverse effects
524 on pregnancy or fetal development and provided complete protection of dams against
525 ZIKV infection and in utero transmission. ZIKV-specific maternal antibodies transferred
526 to the pups through placenta and milk protected the newborns from ZIKV infection
527 (Shan et al., 2019). In the NHP model, DNA-vaccinated dams demonstrated a
528 significant reduction in peak magnitude and duration of viremia, early fetal loss, fetal
529 infection, and placental and fetal brain pathology compared to unvaccinated animals.
530 Vaccine-induced neutralizing antibody titers on the day of first ZIKV exposure were

531 negatively associated with the magnitude of maternal viremia, and the absence of
532 prolonged viremia was associated with better fetal outcomes (Van Rompay et al., 2019).

533 • *SARS-CoV-2*

534 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is a novel coronavirus
535 responsible for the current coronavirus disease 19 (COVID-19) pandemic. Pregnant
536 individuals are at increased risk for severe illness from COVID-19, preterm birth (CDC,
537 2022), stillbirth and other pregnancy complications (Metz et al., 2022). The US licensed
538 BioNTech/Pfizer (BNT162b2) and Moderna (mRNA-1273) messenger RNA two-dose
539 vaccines are currently recommended for pregnant and breastfeeding women and are
540 highly effective at generating neutralizing antibodies (Gray et al., 2021) preventing
541 infection and COVID-19-related hospitalization (Dagan et al., 2021; Goldshtein et al.,
542 2021). Additionally, effectiveness of a 2-dose mRNA COVID-19 vaccine series during
543 pregnancy against COVID-19-associated hospitalization in infants <6 months of age
544 was 61% (95% CI = 31% to 78%) (Halasa et al., 2022). It's worth mentioning that the
545 sample size in this study was too small to assess vaccine effectiveness by pregnancy
546 trimester of vaccination. It is likely that vaccinating in the late second and or third
547 trimester will maximize transplacental transfer of SARS-CoV-2-specific antibodies
548 compared to vaccinating in the first trimester, as demonstrated for influenza
549 immunization during pregnancy (Cunningham et al., 2019).

550

551 • *Mucosal vaccination to boost milk antibodies*

552 Using mucosal vaccination to stimulate mammary gland-trafficking ASCs is a viable
553 strategy to boost breast milk antibodies. Seminal studies in the 1970s first described the
554 'gut-mammary' axis in humans and animals (Bohl et al., 1974; Goldblum et al., 1975)
555 where oral inoculation with bacteria and viruses resulted in an abundance of pathogen-
556 specific IgA plasma cells in the mammary gland and IgA antibodies in milk. Indeed,
557 RSV-specific antibodies were only found in breast milk if rabbits were immunized by oral
558 or transtracheal routes but not intravenously (Peri et al., 1982). Recently, bacteria-
559 coated breast milk IgA was found to modulate neonatal intestinal ROR γ ⁺ T regulatory
560 (Treg) cells during the first days after birth. The levels of Tregs in the neonatal intestine
561 impacted the levels of intestinal IgA as adults, which subsequently impacted levels of
562 bacteria-coated IgA in their milk (Ramanan et al., 2020). This supports a model of multi-
563 generational, noninherited vertical transfer of immunological information via breast milk
564 and highlights the importance of the gut-mammary axis in neonatal health. Trafficking of
565 intestinal ASCs to the mammary gland is likely due to expression of similar homing
566 receptors/ligands like CCR10/CCL28 that exist on lymphocytes found in both the
567 intestine and mammary gland as described earlier. Easily-deliverable immunization
568 strategies like oral tablet vaccines that stimulate IgA⁺ plasmablast/cells (Liebowitz et al.,
569 2020) should be explored to boost breast milk antibodies via the gut-mammary axis and
570 to improve vaccine coverage during pregnancy and lactation (Figure 3).

571

572 *Passive immunization strategies*

573 Recombinant antibodies are an effective strategy against infections when a vaccine is
574 not available for at-risk populations, including pregnant people. The clinical use of

575 monoclonal antibody (mAb) therapy to prevent or treat infection during pregnancy, while
576 limited, has given insights into the safety and efficacy of mAb therapy in the maternal-
577 infant/maternal-neonatal dyad (Figure 3).

578 • *ZIKV*

579 In mouse pregnancy models, passive transfer of neutralizing human monoclonal
580 antibodies (mAbs) reduces ZIKV burden in the placenta and fetal organs as well as fetal
581 demise (Caine et al., 2018; Sapparapu et al., 2016). In a more biological relevant model
582 of ZIKV infection, Van Rompay and colleagues co-administered two recombinant ZIKV-
583 neutralizing antibodies, Z004 and Z021, to pregnant macaques challenged three times
584 with ZIKV during the first and second trimester. While viremia was not entirely
585 eliminated, vertical transmission was limited and the fetuses were spared from
586 neurologic damage (Van Rompay et al., 2020). In a recent study, a potentially neutralizing
587 anti-ZIKV IgM antibody isolated from a ZIKV-infected pregnant woman was protective
588 against lethal ZIKV challenge in nonpregnant mice (Singh et al., 2021). Unlike IgG, IgM
589 is minimally transferred to the fetus, therefore an anti-ZIKV IgM mAb given during
590 pregnancy could circumvent the safety concerns of fetal toxicity and antibody-
591 dependent enhancement of flavivirus disease in a seropositive infant.

592

593 • *CMV*

594 Treatment of CMV with CMV hyperimmune globulin (CMVIG), a plasma-derived
595 preparation of a high amount of CMV polyclonal immunoglobulins, has been studied for
596 the prevention of fetal infection. Two randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind

597 studies did not find that CMVIG decreased the incidence of infant infection (Hughes et
598 al., 2021; Revello et al., 2014). While a previous report suggested that a biweekly
599 (rather than monthly) administration of CMVIG may be more effective at reducing cCMV
600 (Kagan et al., 2019), this study was neither blinded or randomized and the comparison
601 group was a historical cohort making it difficult to draw conclusions. It is likely that the
602 lack of efficacy observed in the randomized, placebo-controlled studies is due to the
603 poor neutralizing activity of CMVIG (Planitzer et al., 2011) or inappropriate binding the
604 surface glycoprotein B (gB). Indeed, in a cohort of CMV gB/MF59 vaccine recipient's
605 serum IgG binding to gB on a cell surface rather than the soluble vaccine antigen was
606 associated with protection against primary CMV infection (Jenks et al., 2020).
607 Therefore, further investigation into gB-specific mAbs that recognize cell-associated gB
608 is warranted for the development of efficacious antibody therapies against cCMV.
609 Additionally, non-neutralizing antibody functions like ADCP have recently been
610 associated with decreased risk of cCMV infection (Semmes et al., 2021b). These results
611 suggest that non-neutralizing IgG function against gB in its native confirmation may
612 protect against CMV infection and should be considered when development mAb
613 therapies to prevent cCMV.

614

615 • *SARS-CoV-2*

616 The increased risk of pregnancy complications following SARS-CoV-2 infection led to
617 the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to expand the emergency use
618 authorization of anti-spike mAb therapy for the outpatient treatment of mild-to-moderate
619 COVID-19 to pregnant individuals. Indeed, guidelines from the National Institutes of

620 Health, the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, and the Society for
621 Maternal-Fetal Medicine suggest that women should be considered for receiving mAb
622 therapy. However, there are limited clinical data on its use in pregnant women. A 2020
623 report highlighted four unvaccinated pregnant individuals with COVID-19 who were
624 treated one in the second and one in the third trimester with REGN-COV-2, a
625 combination of casirivimab and imdevimab mAbs (Mayer et al., 2021). There were no
626 adverse drug reactions and both women recovered without developing severe COVID-
627 19. Additionally, a case series of 51 pregnant women who received either bamlaniviab
628 (14%), bamlanivimab-etesevimab (7%) or casirivimab-imdevimab (79%) anti-spike mAb
629 therapy for mild-to-moderate COVID-19 at a mean gestational age at infusion of
630 25.7 ± 10.1 weeks (Thilagar et al., 2022). There were no immediate adverse effects and
631 no patient had COVID-19 progression. While infant blood was not taken in either study,
632 it is likely these antibodies crossed the placenta into fetal circulation, particularly if
633 antibodies were given in the second or third trimester. Indeed, women who are
634 seropositive efficiently transfer SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies across the placenta and
635 cord blood concentrations are directly associated with maternal antibody
636 concentrations.

637

638 **Postnatal**

639

640 Postnatal delivery of therapeutic mAbs for the treatment of infant disease can be
641 delivered by three routes; orally to infants, systemically to infants or via human milk.

642

643 *Infant delivery of mAbs via oral route*

644 Oral administration of recombinant mAbs has the potential to treat enteric infections in
645 infants. Indeed, multiple animal studies have demonstrated efficacy of oral
646 administration of mAbs to protect against enteric diseases including *Salmonella*
647 *enterica* serovar Typhimurium (STm), *Campylobacter jejuni* (*C. jejuni*),
648 enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), and rotavirus all leading causes of moderate-
649 to-severe diarrhea in children. Perruzza and colleagues orally gavaged recently weaned
650 mice with recombinant anti-*C. jejuni* flagellar capping protein (FliD) sIgA1 and sIgA2
651 prior to infection with *C. jejuni* (Perruzza et al., 2020). Equal protection and accelerated
652 clearance against *C. jejuni* infection was observed between the two subclasses.
653 Interestingly, prophylactic anti-FliD IgG did not protect against *C. jejuni* infection, likely
654 due to its shorter half-life in the intestine. Multiple studies have evaluated the efficacy of
655 orally administered recombinant sIgA mAbs against experimental ETEC infection in
656 mice and nonhuman primate models. In NHPs (*Aotus nancymaae*), oral administration
657 of antibodies to the ETEC adhesin subunit CfaE at 9 mg/kg prior to ETEC infection
658 resulted in decreased diarrhea, although no differences in fecal shedding were
659 observed (Stoppato et al., 2020). Oral administration of recombinant monoclonal
660 dimeric IgA (dIgA) and secreted IgA (sIgA) against *Salmonella enterica* serovar
661 Typhimurium (STm) limited infection and uptake into the Peyer's Patches after STm
662 challenge, although no differences were observed between dIgA or sIgA antibodies
663 (Richards et al., 2020). Lastly, murine studies have demonstrated that mAbs with
664 heterotypic specificity could mediate protection against one or several rotavirus
665 serotypes (Matsui et al., 1989; Offit et al., 1986) and prophylaxis with a rice-based oral

666 antibody fragment containing a neutralizing antibody domain protected against rotavirus
667 infection (Tokuhara et al., 2013).

668

669 *Infant delivery of mAbs via systemic route*

670 The most common use of therapeutic mAbs during the postpartum period is in the
671 treatment of RSV. Intramuscular (IM) administration of palivizumab, a mAb to the RSV F
672 protein, reduced the risk of hospitalization for RSV-associated lower respiratory tract
673 infection among premature infants and among full-term infants with chronic lung disease
674 or congenital heart disease (Groothuis et al., 1993). Palivizumab is available as a
675 prophylaxis administered in five monthly injections for infants who are at highest risk for
676 serious RSV sequelae. Motavizumab, a higher-potency mAb derived from palivizumab,
677 reduced the risk of RSV-associated lower respiratory tract infections and
678 hospitalizations among full-term American Indian infants (O'Brien et al., 2015). Recently,
679 nirsevimab, a mAb with enhanced neutralizing activity compared to palivizumab and
680 modification of the Fc region to promote extension of half-life, given IM as a single dose
681 resulted in fewer medically attended RSV-associated lower respiratory tract infections
682 and hospitalizations compared to placebo in health preterm infants (Griffin et al., 2020).
683 In this study, adverse side effects were similar in both treatment groups.

684 For the treatment of SARS-CoV-2, the U.S. FDA expanded authorization of
685 bamlanivimab and etesevimab to all pediatric patients, including newborns. While there
686 are currently no reports of safety or efficacy of anti-Spike mAbs for the prevention of
687 SARS-CoV-2 infection or COVID-19, clinical trials using anti-RSV mAbs suggest these

688 mAbs will be well-tolerated and result in fewer instances of symptomatic SARS-CoV-2
689 infections and hospitalizations.

690

691 *Infant delivery of mAbs via maternal milk*

692 Maternal passive transfer of recombinant mAbs into breast milk is a viable strategy for
693 delivering potentially neutralizing antibodies to suckling infants. Fouda and colleagues
694 demonstrated that systemic administration of rhesus recombinant IgG, monomeric IgA
695 (mIgA) and dIgA versions of HIV-specific, bnAb b12 (RhB12) all trafficked to milk
696 however the dIgA RhB12 concentration was 1-2 logs higher compared to IgG and mIgA
697 RhB12 (Fouda et al., 2017). Additionally, while HIV neutralization was detected in the
698 plasma of all animals, only those infused with RhB12 dIgA demonstrated moderate
699 levels of virus neutralization in milk. Similarly, a recent report showed that a
700 recombinant potentially rotavirus neutralizing dIgA could traffic to milk after maternal
701 systemic administration and protected suckling pups against human rotavirus-induced
702 diarrhea (Langel et al., 2021). However, the half-life of dIgA in vivo was only 1.5-3 days.
703 Therefore, there is a need for mAb delivery platforms that can persistently deliver dIgA
704 in vivo including integrase-defective lentiviral vectors, recombinant DNA, or mRNA
705 strategies.

706

707 **Conclusions**

708 The maternal immune system has evolved to transfer immune protection to its
709 developing offspring against infectious agents in its environment. Immune components
710 delivered transplacentally and through human milk while unique in their delivery method

711 work in concert to fine-tune the maternal, neonatal, and infant immune responses.
712 However, pathogens have evolved mechanisms to evade these immune responses
713 resulting in significant fetal and neonatal morbidity and mortality. Therefore, it is
714 paramount that the maternal-neonatal dyad is not left beyond during key times of drug
715 and therapeutic development. The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic again highlighted how
716 pregnant women and children are some of the last populations to have access to life-
717 saving therapeutics. Precision vaccines and mAb development will provide opportunities
718 to prevent disease, limit the spread of infectious agents, and promote long term health
719 in the maternal-neonatal dyad.

720

721 **References**

722

723 (2012). Vaccines against influenza WHO position paper - November 2012. *Wkly Epidemiol Rec*
724 *87*, 461-476.

725 Akhter, H., Aziz, F., Ullah, F.R., Ahsan, M., and Islam, S.N. (2021). Immunoglobulins content in
726 colostrum, transitional and mature milk of Bangladeshi mothers: Influence of parity and
727 sociodemographic characteristics. *J Mother Child* *24*, 8-15.

728 Albrecht, M., Pagenkemper, M., Wiessner, C., Spohn, M., Lütgehetmann, M., Jacobsen, H.,
729 Gabriel, G., Zazara, D.E., Haertel, C., Hecher, K., *et al.* (2021). Infant immunity against viral
730 infections is advanced by the placenta-dependent vertical transfer of maternal antibodies.
731 *Vaccine*.

732 Ander, S.E., Diamond, M.S., and Coyne, C.B. (2019). Immune responses at the maternal-fetal
733 interface. *Science immunology* *4*.

734 Armistead, B., Jiang, Y., Carlson, M., Ford, E.S., Jani, S., Houck, J., Wu, X., Pecor, T., Kachikis,
735 A., Yeung, W., *et al.* (2021). Mucosal memory T cells in breastmilk are modulated by SARS-
736 CoV-2 mRNA vaccination. 2021.2012.2003.21267036.

737 Atwell, J.E., Thumar, B., Robinson, L.J., Toby, R., Yambo, P., Ome-Kaius, M., Siba, P.M.,
738 Unger, H.W., Rogerson, S.J., King, C.L., *et al.* (2016). Impact of Placental Malaria and
739 Hypergammaglobulinemia on Transplacental Transfer of Respiratory Syncytial Virus Antibody in
740 Papua New Guinea. *The Journal of infectious diseases* *213*, 423-431.

741 Balle, C., Armistead, B., Kiravu, A., Song, X., Happel, A.-U., Hoffmann, A., Kanaan, S.B.,
742 Nelson, J.L., Gray, C.M., Jaspan, H.B., *et al.* (2022). Factors influencing maternal
743 microchimerism throughout infancy and its impact on infant T cell immunity.
744 2021.2003.2002.432825.

745 Balle, C., Kiravu, A., Hoffmann, A., Happel, A.-U., Kanaan, S.B., Nelson, J.L., Gray, C.M.,
746 Jaspan, H.B., and Harrington, W.E. (2021). Factors influencing maternal microchimerism
747 throughout infancy and its impact on infant T cell immunity. 2021.2003.2002.432825.

748 Battersby, A.J., Khara, J., Wright, V.J., Levy, O., and Kampmann, B. (2016). Antimicrobial
749 Proteins and Peptides in Early Life: Ontogeny and Translational Opportunities. *Frontiers in*
750 *immunology* 7, 309.

751 Bautista-Marquez, A., Velasquez, D.E., Esparza-Aguilar, M., Luna-Cruz, M., Ruiz-Moran, T.,
752 Sugata, K., Jiang, B., Parashar, U., Patel, M., and Richardson, V. (2016). Breastfeeding linked
753 to the reduction of both rotavirus shedding and IgA levels after Rotarix® immunization in
754 Mexican infants. *Vaccine* 34, 5284-5289.

755 Bohl, E.H., Gupta, R.K., Olquin, M.V., and Saif, L.J. (1972). Antibody responses in serum,
756 colostrum, and milk of swine after infection or vaccination with transmissible gastroenteritis
757 virus. *Infection and immunity* 6, 289-301.

758 Bohl, E.H., Saif, L.J., Gupta, R.K., and Frederick, G.T. (1974). Secretory antibodies in milk of
759 swine against transmissible gastroenteritis virus. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 45, 337-342.

760 Bongertz, V., Costa, C.I., Veloso, V.G., Grinsztejn, B., Filho, E.C., Calvet, G., and Pilotto, J.H.
761 (2002). Neutralization titres and vertical HIV-1 transmission. *Scand J Immunol* 56, 642-644.

762 Borghi, S., Bournazos, S., Thulin, N.K., Li, C., Gajewski, A., Sherwood, R.W., Zhang, S., Harris,
763 E., Jagannathan, P., Wang, L.X., *et al.* (2020). FcRn, but not FcγRs, drives maternal-fetal
764 transplacental transport of human IgG antibodies. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 117, 12943-12951.

765 Boudreau, C.M., and Alter, G. (2019). Extra-Neutralizing FcR-Mediated Antibody Functions for a
766 Universal Influenza Vaccine. *Frontiers in immunology* 10, 440.

767 Boudreau, C.M., Burke, J.S.t., Shuey, K.D., Wolf, C., Katz, J., Tielsch, J., Khatry, S., LeClerq,
768 S.C., Englund, J.A., Chu, H.Y., *et al.* (2022). Dissecting Fc signatures of protection in neonates
769 following maternal influenza vaccination in a placebo-controlled trial. *Cell reports* 38, 110337.

770 Bournazos, S., Gupta, A., and Ravetch, J.V. (2020). The role of IgG Fc receptors in antibody-
771 dependent enhancement. *Nature Reviews Immunology* 20, 633-643.

772 Braathen, R., Sorensen, V., Brandtzaeg, P., Sandlie, I., and Johansen, F.E. (2002). The
773 carboxyl-terminal domains of IgA and IgM direct isotype-specific polymerization and interaction
774 with the polymeric immunoglobulin receptor. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 277, 42755-
775 42762.

776 Caballero-Flores, G., Sakamoto, K., Zeng, M.Y., Wang, Y., Hakim, J., Matus-Acuña, V.,
777 Inohara, N., and Núñez, G. (2019). Maternal Immunization Confers Protection to the Offspring
778 against an Attaching and Effacing Pathogen through Delivery of IgG in Breast Milk. *Cell host &*
779 *microbe* 25, 313-323.e314.

780 Caine, E.A., Jagger, B.W., and Diamond, M.S. (2018). Animal Models of Zika Virus Infection
781 during Pregnancy. *Viruses* 10.

782 Cazac, B.B., and Roes, J. (2000). TGF-beta receptor controls B cell responsiveness and
783 induction of IgA in vivo. *Immunity* 13, 443-451.

784 CDC (2022). Pregnant and Recently Pregnant People At Increased Risk for Severe Illness from
785 COVID-19.

786 Cerutti, A. (2008). The regulation of IgA class switching. *Nature reviews Immunology* 8, 421-
787 434.

788 Cianga, P., Medesan, C., Richardson, J.A., Ghetie, V., and Ward, E.S. (1999). Identification and
789 function of neonatal Fc receptor in mammary gland of lactating mice. *European journal of*
790 *immunology* 29, 2515-2523.

791 Clements, T., Rice, T.F., Vamvakas, G., Barnett, S., Barnes, M., Donaldson, B., Jones, C.E.,
792 Kampmann, B., and Holder, B. (2020). Update on Transplacental Transfer of IgG Subclasses:
793 Impact of Maternal and Fetal Factors. *Frontiers in immunology* 11, 1920.

794 Cunningham, W., Geard, N., Fielding, J.E., Braat, S., Madhi, S.A., Nunes, M.C., Christian, L.M.,
795 Lin, S.Y., Lee, C.N., Yamaguchi, K., *et al.* (2019). Optimal timing of influenza vaccine during
796 pregnancy: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Influenza and other respiratory viruses* 13,
797 438-452.

798 Czosnykowska-Łukacka, M., Lis-Kuberka, J., Królak-Olejnik, B., and Orczyk-Pawłowicz, M.
799 (2020). Changes in Human Milk Immunoglobulin Profile During Prolonged Lactation. *8*.
800 Dabrera, G., Zhao, H., Andrews, N., Begum, F., Green, H., Ellis, J., Elias, K., Donati, M.,
801 Zambon, M., and Pebody, R. (2014). Effectiveness of seasonal influenza vaccination during
802 pregnancy in preventing influenza infection in infants, England, 2013/14. *Euro Surveill 19*,
803 20959.

804 Dagan, N., Barda, N., Biron-Shental, T., Makov-Assif, M., Key, C., Kohane, I.S., Hernán, M.A.,
805 Lipsitch, M., Hernandez-Diaz, S., Reis, B.Y., *et al.* (2021). Effectiveness of the BNT162b2
806 mRNA COVID-19 vaccine in pregnancy. *Nat Med 27*, 1693-1695.

807 Darby, M.G., Chetty, A., Mrjden, D., Rolot, M., Smith, K., Mackowiak, C., Sedda, D., Nyangahu,
808 D., Jaspan, H., Toellner, K.M., *et al.* (2019). Pre-conception maternal helminth infection
809 transfers via nursing long-lasting cellular immunity against helminths to offspring. *Science*
810 *advances 5*, eaav3058.

811 De Groot, N., Van Kuik-Romeijn, P., Lee, S.H., and De Boer, H.A. (2000). Increased
812 immunoglobulin A levels in milk by over-expressing the murine polymeric immunoglobulin
813 receptor gene in the mammary gland epithelial cells of transgenic mice. *Immunology 101*, 218-
814 224.

815 de Moraes-Pinto, M.I., Verhoeff, F., Chimsuku, L., Milligan, P.J., Wesumperuma, L., Broadhead,
816 R.L., Brabin, B.J., Johnson, P.M., and Hart, C.A. (1998). Placental antibody transfer: influence
817 of maternal HIV infection and placental malaria. *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed 79*, F202-205.

818 de Taeye, S.W., Ozorowski, G., Torrents de la Pena, A., Guttman, M., Julien, J.P., van den
819 Kerkhof, T.L., Burger, J.A., Pritchard, L.K., Pugach, P., Yasmeen, A., *et al.* (2015).
820 Immunogenicity of Stabilized HIV-1 Envelope Trimers with Reduced Exposure of Non-
821 neutralizing Epitopes. *Cell 163*, 1702-1715.

822 Dechavanne, C., Dechavanne, S., Sadissou, I., Lokossou, A.G., Alvarado, F., Dambrun, M.,
823 Moutairou, K., Courtin, D., Nuel, G., Garcia, A., *et al.* (2017). Associations between an IgG3
824 polymorphism in the binding domain for FcRn, transplacental transfer of malaria-specific IgG3,
825 and protection against *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria during infancy: A birth cohort study in
826 Benin. *PLoS medicine 14*, e1002403.

827 Demicheli, V., Barale, A., and Rivetti, A. (2015). Vaccines for women for preventing neonatal
828 tetanus. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews 2015*, Cd002959.

829 Dorfman, J.R., Balla, S.R., Pathirana, J., Groome, M.J., Madhi, S.A., and Moore, P.L. (2021). In
830 Utero Human Cytomegalovirus Infection Is Associated With Increased Levels of Putatively
831 Protective Maternal Antibodies in Nonprimary Infection: Evidence for Boosting but Not
832 Protection. *Clinical infectious diseases : an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society*
833 *of America 73*, e981-e987.

834 Doyle, T.J., Goodin, K., and Hamilton, J.J. (2013). Maternal and neonatal outcomes among
835 pregnant women with 2009 pandemic influenza A(H1N1) illness in Florida, 2009-2010: a
836 population-based cohort study. *PLoS One 8*, e79040.

837 Eibl, M.M., Wolf, H.M., Fürnkranz, H., and Rosenkranz, A. (1988). Prevention of necrotizing
838 enterocolitis in low-birth-weight infants by IgA-IgG feeding. *The New England journal of*
839 *medicine 319*, 1-7.

840 El Guerche-Seblain, C., Moureau, A., Schiffler, C., Dupuy, M., Pepin, S., Samson, S.I.,
841 Vanhems, P., and Schellevis, F. (2019). Epidemiology and burden of influenza in healthy
842 children aged 6 to 35 months: analysis of data from the placebo arm of a phase III efficacy trial.
843 *BMC Infect Dis 19*, 308.

844 Foster, J.P., Seth, R., and Cole, M.J. (2016). Oral immunoglobulin for preventing necrotizing
845 enterocolitis in preterm and low birth weight neonates. *The Cochrane database of systematic*
846 *reviews 4*, Cd001816.

847 Fouda, G.G., Eudailey, J., Kunz, E.L., Amos, J.D., Liebl, B.E., Himes, J., Boakye-Agyeman, F.,
848 Beck, K., Michaels, A.J., Cohen-Wolkowicz, M., *et al.* (2017). Systemic administration of an

849 HIV-1 broadly neutralizing dimeric IgA yields mucosal secretory IgA and virus neutralization.
850 Mucosal immunology 10, 228-237.

851 Fouda, G.G., Jaeger, F.H., Amos, J.D., Ho, C., Kunz, E.L., Anasti, K., Stamper, L.W., Liebl,
852 B.E., Barbas, K.H., Ohashi, T., *et al.* (2013a). Tenascin-C is an innate broad-spectrum, HIV-1–
853 neutralizing protein in breast milk. *110*, 18220-18225.

854 Fouda, G.G., Mahlokozera, T., Salazar-Gonzalez, J.F., Salazar, M.G., Learn, G., Kumar, S.B.,
855 Dennison, S.M., Russell, E., Rizzolo, K., Jaeger, F., *et al.* (2013b). Postnatally-transmitted HIV-
856 1 Envelope variants have similar neutralization-sensitivity and function to that of nontransmitted
857 breast milk variants. *Retrovirology* 10, 3.

858 Fouda, G.G., Martinez, D.R., Swamy, G.K., and Permar, S.R. (2018). The Impact of IgG
859 transplacental transfer on early life immunity. *Immunohorizons* 2, 14-25.

860 Garofalo, R. (2010). Cytokines in human milk. *The Journal of pediatrics* 156, S36-40.

861 Gaudinski, M.R., Houser, K.V., Morabito, K.M., Hu, Z., Yamshchikov, G., Rothwell, R.S.,
862 Berkowitz, N., Mendoza, F., Saunders, J.G., Novik, L., *et al.* (2018). Safety, tolerability, and
863 immunogenicity of two Zika virus DNA vaccine candidates in healthy adults: randomised, open-
864 label, phase 1 clinical trials. *Lancet (London, England)* 391, 552-562.

865 Gautam, R., Nishimura, Y., Pegu, A., Nason, M.C., Klein, F., Gazumyan, A., Golijanin, J.,
866 Buckler-White, A., Sadjadpour, R., Wang, K., *et al.* (2016). A single injection of anti-HIV-1
867 antibodies protects against repeated SHIV challenges. *Nature* 533, 105-109.

868 Ghulam-Smith, M., Olson, A., White, L.F., Chasela, C.S., Ellington, S.R., Kourtis, A.P.,
869 Jamieson, D.J., Tegha, G., van der Horst, C.M., and Sagar, M. (2017). Maternal but Not Infant
870 Anti-HIV-1 Neutralizing Antibody Response Associates with Enhanced Transmission and Infant
871 Morbidity. *MBio* 8.

872 Goderis, J., De Leenheer, E., Smets, K., Van Hoecke, H., Keymeulen, A., and Dhooge, I.
873 (2014). Hearing loss and congenital CMV infection: a systematic review. *Pediatrics* 134, 972-
874 982.

875 Goldblum, R.M., Ahlstedt, S., Carlsson, B., Hanson, L.A., Jodal, U., Lidin-Janson, G., and Sohl-
876 Akerlund, A. (1975). Antibody-forming cells in human colostrum after oral immunisation. *Nature*
877 257, 797-798.

878 Goldshtein, I., Nevo, D., Steinberg, D.M., Rotem, R.S., Gorfine, M., Chodick, G., and Segal, Y.
879 (2021). Association Between BNT162b2 Vaccination and Incidence of SARS-CoV-2 Infection in
880 Pregnant Women. *Jama* 326, 728-735.

881 Gopalakrishna, K.P., Macadangdang, B.R., Rogers, M.B., Tometich, J.T., Firek, B.A., Baker, R.,
882 Ji, J., Burr, A.H.P., Ma, C., Good, M., *et al.* (2019). Maternal IgA protects against the
883 development of necrotizing enterocolitis in preterm infants. *Nat Med* 25, 1110-1115.

884 Gray, K.J., Bordt, E.A., Atyeo, C., Deriso, E., Akinwunmi, B., Young, N., Baez, A.M., Shook,
885 L.L., Cvrk, D., James, K., *et al.* (2021). Coronavirus disease 2019 vaccine response in pregnant
886 and lactating women: a cohort study. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 225,
887 303.e301-303.e317.

888 Griffin, M.P., Yuan, Y., Takas, T., Domachowske, J.B., Madhi, S.A., Manzoni, P., Simões,
889 E.A.F., Esser, M.T., Khan, A.A., Dubovsky, F., *et al.* (2020). Single-Dose Nirsevimab for
890 Prevention of RSV in Preterm Infants. *The New England journal of medicine* 383, 415-425.

891 Groothuis, J.R., Simoes, E.A., Levin, M.J., Hall, C.B., Long, C.E., Rodriguez, W.J., Arrobio, J.,
892 Meissner, H.C., Fulton, D.R., Welliver, R.C., *et al.* (1993). Prophylactic administration of
893 respiratory syncytial virus immune globulin to high-risk infants and young children. The
894 Respiratory Syncytial Virus Immune Globulin Study Group. *The New England journal of*
895 *medicine* 329, 1524-1530.

896 Halasa, N.B., Olson, S.M., Staat, M.A., Newhams, M.M., Price, A.M., Boom, J.A., Sahni, L.C.,
897 Cameron, M.A., Pannaraj, P.S., Bline, K.E., *et al.* (2022). Effectiveness of Maternal Vaccination
898 with mRNA COVID-19 Vaccine During Pregnancy Against COVID-19-Associated Hospitalization

899 in Infants Aged <6 Months - 17 States, July 2021-January 2022. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*
900 *71*, 264-270.

901 Hall, J.M., Lingenfelter, P., Adams, S.L., Lasser, D., Hansen, J.A., and Bean, M.A. (1995).
902 Detection of maternal cells in human umbilical cord blood using fluorescence in situ
903 hybridization. *Blood* *86*, 2829-2832.

904 Haller, D., Holt, L., Kim, S.C., Schwabe, R.F., Sartor, R.B., and Jobin, C. (2003). Transforming
905 growth factor-beta 1 inhibits non-pathogenic Gram negative bacteria-induced NF-kappa B
906 recruitment to the interleukin-6 gene promoter in intestinal epithelial cells through modulation of
907 histone acetylation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* *278*, 23851-23860.

908 Harrington, W.E., Kanaan, S.B., Muehlenbachs, A., Morrison, R., Stevenson, P., Fried, M.,
909 Duffy, P.E., and Nelson, J.L. (2017). Maternal Microchimerism Predicts Increased Infection but
910 Decreased Disease due to *Plasmodium falciparum* During Early Childhood. *The Journal of*
911 *infectious diseases* *215*, 1445-1451.

912 Hassiotou, F., Geddes, D.T., and Hartmann, P.E. (2013a). Cells in human milk: state of the
913 science. *Journal of human lactation : official journal of International Lactation Consultant*
914 *Association* *29*, 171-182.

915 Hassiotou, F., Hepworth, A.R., Metzger, P., Tat Lai, C., Trengove, N., Hartmann, P.E., and
916 Filgueira, L. (2013b). Maternal and infant infections stimulate a rapid leukocyte response in
917 breastmilk. *Clinical & translational immunology* *2*, e3.

918 Hester, S.N., Chen, X., Li, M., Monaco, M.H., Comstock, S.S., Kuhlenschmidt, T.B.,
919 Kuhlenschmidt, M.S., and Donovan, S.M. (2013). Human milk oligosaccharides inhibit rotavirus
920 infectivity in vitro and in acutely infected piglets. *The British journal of nutrition* *110*, 1233-1242.

921 Hompe, E.D., Mangold, J.F., Kumar, A., Eudailey, J.A., McGuire, E., Haynes, B.F., Moody,
922 M.A., Wright, P.F., Fouda, G.G., Giorgi, E.E., *et al.* (2020). Induction of Neutralizing Responses
923 against Autologous Virus in Maternal HIV Vaccine Trials. *mSphere* *5*.

924 Hughes, B.L., Clifton, R.G., Rouse, D.J., Saade, G.R., Dinsmoor, M.J., Reddy, U.M., Pass, R.,
925 Allard, D., Mallett, G., Fette, L.M., *et al.* (2021). A Trial of Hyperimmune Globulin to Prevent
926 Congenital Cytomegalovirus Infection. *The New England journal of medicine* *385*, 436-444.

927 Hurley, W.L., and Theil, P.K. (2011). Perspectives on immunoglobulins in colostrum and milk.
928 *Nutrients* *3*, 442-474.

929 Inoue, N., Abe, M., Kobayashi, R., and Yamada, S. (2018). Vaccine Development for
930 Cytomegalovirus. *Adv Exp Med Biol* *1045*, 271-296.

931 Jarvis, J.R., Dorey, R.B., Warricker, F.D.M., Alwan, N.A., and Jones, C.E. (2020). The
932 effectiveness of influenza vaccination in pregnancy in relation to child health outcomes:
933 Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Vaccine* *38*, 1601-1613.

934 Jenks, J.A., Nelson, C.S., Roark, H.K., Goodwin, M.L., Pass, R.F., Bernstein, D.I., Walter, E.B.,
935 Edwards, K.M., Wang, D., Fu, T.M., *et al.* (2020). Antibody binding to native cytomegalovirus
936 glycoprotein B predicts efficacy of the gB/MF59 vaccine in humans. *Science translational*
937 *medicine* *12*.

938 Jennewein, M.F., Goldfarb, I., Dolatshahi, S., Cosgrove, C., Noelette, F.J., Krykbaeva, M., Das,
939 J., Sarkar, A., Gorman, M.J., Fischinger, S., *et al.* (2019). Fc Glycan-Mediated Regulation of
940 Placental Antibody Transfer. *Cell* *178*, 202-215.e214.

941 Johansen, F.E., and Kaetzel, C.S. (2011). Regulation of the polymeric immunoglobulin receptor
942 and IgA transport: new advances in environmental factors that stimulate plgR expression and its
943 role in mucosal immunity. *Mucosal immunology* *4*, 598-602.

944 John, S., Yuzhakov, O., Woods, A., Deterling, J., Hassett, K., Shaw, C.A., and Ciaramella, G.
945 (2018). Multi-antigenic human cytomegalovirus mRNA vaccines that elicit potent humoral and
946 cell-mediated immunity. *Vaccine* *36*, 1689-1699.

947 Jonsson, A.M., Uzunel, M., Götherström, C., Papadogiannakis, N., and Westgren, M. (2008).
948 Maternal microchimerism in human fetal tissues. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology*
949 *198*, 325.e321-326.

950 Kagan, K.O., Enders, M., Schampera, M.S., Baeumel, E., Hoopmann, M., Geipel, A., Berg, C.,
951 Goelz, R., De Catte, L., Wallwiener, D., *et al.* (2019). Prevention of maternal-fetal transmission
952 of cytomegalovirus after primary maternal infection in the first trimester by biweekly
953 hyperimmunoglobulin administration. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol* 53, 383-389.

954 Kallolimath, S., Sun, L., Palt, R., Stiasny, K., Mayrhofer, P., Gruber, C., Kogelmann, B., Chen,
955 Q., and Steinkellner, H. (2021). Highly active engineered IgG3 antibodies against SARS-CoV-2.
956 *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 118.

957 Kanaan, S.B., Gammill, H.S., Harrington, W.E., De Rosa, S.C., Stevenson, P.A., Forsyth, A.M.,
958 Allen, J., Cousin, E., van Besien, K., Delaney, C.S., *et al.* (2017). Maternal microchimerism is
959 prevalent in cord blood in memory T cells and other cell subsets, and persists post-transplant.
960 *Oncoimmunology* 6, e1311436-e1311436.

961 Kinder, J.M., Jiang, T.T., Ertelt, J.M., Xin, L., Strong, B.S., Shaaban, A.F., and Way, S.S.
962 (2015). Cross-Generational Reproductive Fitness Enforced by Microchimeric Maternal Cells.
963 *Cell* 162, 505-515.

964 Kinder, J.M., Stelzer, I.A., Arck, P.C., and Way, S.S. (2017). Immunological implications of
965 pregnancy-induced microchimerism. *Nature reviews Immunology* 17, 483-494.

966 Konkel, J.E., and Chen, W. (2011). Balancing acts: the role of TGF- β in the mucosal immune
967 system. *Trends in molecular medicine* 17, 668-676.

968 Korpe, P.S., Liu, Y., Siddique, A., Kabir, M., Ralston, K., Ma, J.Z., Haque, R., and Petri, W.A.,
969 Jr. (2013). Breast milk parasite-specific antibodies and protection from amebiasis and
970 cryptosporidiosis in Bangladeshi infants: a prospective cohort study. *Clinical infectious diseases*
971 : an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America 56, 988-992.

972 Kourtis, A.P., Ibegbu, C.C., Theiler, R., Xu, Y.X., Bansil, P., Jamieson, D.J., Lindsay, M., Butera,
973 S., and Duerr, A. (2007). Breast milk CD4+ T cells express high levels of C chemokine receptor
974 5 and CXC chemokine receptor 4 and are preserved in HIV-infected mothers receiving highly
975 active antiretroviral therapy. *The Journal of infectious diseases* 195, 965-972.

976 Kumar, A., Giorgi, E.E., Tu, J.J., Martinez, D.R., Eudailey, J., Mengual, M., Honnayakanahalli
977 Marichannegowda, M., Van Dyke, R., Gao, F., and Permar, S.R. (2021). Mutations that confer
978 resistance to broadly-neutralizing antibodies define HIV-1 variants of transmitting mothers from
979 that of non-transmitting mothers. *PLoS Pathog* 17, e1009478.

980 Kurtis, J.D., Raj, D.K., Michelow, I.C., Park, S., Nixon, C.E., McDonald, E.A., Nixon, C.P., Pond-
981 Tor, S., Jha, A., Taliano, R.J., *et al.* (2019). Maternally-derived Antibodies to Schizont Egress
982 Antigen-1 and Protection of Infants From Severe Malaria. *Clinical infectious diseases : an*
983 *official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America* 68, 1718-1724.

984 Kwong, P.D., Doyle, M.L., Casper, D.J., Cicala, C., Leavitt, S.A., Majeed, S., Steenbeke, T.D.,
985 Venturi, M., Chaiken, I., Fung, M., *et al.* (2002). HIV-1 evades antibody-mediated neutralization
986 through conformational masking of receptor-binding sites. *Nature* 420, 678-682.

987 Lamprecht, C.L., Krause, H.E., and Mufson, M.A. (1976). Role of maternal antibody in
988 pneumonia and bronchiolitis due to respiratory syncytial virus. *The Journal of infectious*
989 *diseases* 134, 211-217.

990 Langel, S., Steppe, J., Chang, J., Travieso, T., Webster, H., Otero, C., Williamson, L., Crowe, J.,
991 Greenberg, H., Wu, H., *et al.* (2021). Protective Transfer: Maternal passive immunization with a
992 rotavirus-neutralizing dimeric IgA protects against rotavirus disease in suckling neonates.
993 2021.2009.2021.461116.

994 Langel, S.N., Wark, W.A., Garst, S.N., James, R.E., McGilliard, M.L., Petersson-Wolfe, C.S.,
995 and Kanevsky-Mullarky, I. (2015). Effect of feeding whole compared with cell-free colostrum on
996 calf immune status: The neonatal period. *Journal of dairy science* 98, 3729-3740.

997 Laucirica, D.R., Triantis, V., Schoemaker, R., Estes, M.K., and Ramani, S. (2017). Milk
998 Oligosaccharides Inhibit Human Rotavirus Infectivity in MA104 Cells. *The Journal of nutrition*
999 147, 1709-1714.

1000 Le Doare, K., Bellis, K., Faal, A., Birt, J., Munblit, D., Humphries, H., Taylor, S., Warburton, F.,
1001 Heath, P.T., Kampmann, B., *et al.* (2017). SIgA, TGF- β 1, IL-10, and TNF α in Colostrum Are
1002 Associated with Infant Group B Streptococcus Colonization. *Frontiers in immunology* 8, 1269.
1003 Liebowitz, D., Gottlieb, K., Kolhatkar, N.S., Garg, S.J., Asher, J.M., Nazareno, J., Kim, K.,
1004 McIlwain, D.R., and Tucker, S.N. (2020). Efficacy, immunogenicity, and safety of an oral
1005 influenza vaccine: a placebo-controlled and active-controlled phase 2 human challenge study.
1006 *The Lancet Infectious diseases* 20, 435-444.
1007 Lindner, C., Thomsen, I., Wahl, B., Ugur, M., Sethi, M.K., Friedrichsen, M., Smoczek, A., Ott, S.,
1008 Baumann, U., Suerbaum, S., *et al.* (2015). Diversification of memory B cells drives the
1009 continuous adaptation of secretory antibodies to gut microbiota. *Nature immunology* 16, 880-
1010 888.
1011 Lozano, N.A., Lozano, A., Marini, V., Saranz, R.J., Blumberg, R.S., Baker, K., Agresta, M.F.,
1012 and Ponzio, M.F. (2018). Expression of FcRn receptor in placental tissue and its relationship
1013 with IgG levels in term and preterm newborns. *American journal of reproductive immunology*
1014 (New York, NY : 1989) 80, e12972.
1015 Lu, L.L., Suscovich, T.J., Fortune, S.M., and Alter, G. (2018). Beyond binding: antibody effector
1016 functions in infectious diseases. *Nature Reviews Immunology* 18, 46-61.
1017 Lu, W., Zhao, Z., Zhao, Y., Yu, S., Zhao, Y., Fan, B., Kacszkovics, I., Hammarström, L., and Li,
1018 N. (2007). Over-expression of the bovine FcRn in the mammary gland results in increased IgG
1019 levels in both milk and serum of transgenic mice. *Immunology* 122, 401-408.
1020 Lucas, A., and Cole, T.J. (1990). Breast milk and neonatal necrotising enterocolitis. *Lancet*
1021 (London, England) 336, 1519-1523.
1022 Mabuka, J., Nduati, R., Odem-Davis, K., Peterson, D., and Overbaugh, J. (2012). HIV-specific
1023 antibodies capable of ADCC are common in breastmilk and are associated with reduced risk of
1024 transmission in women with high viral loads. *PLoS Pathog* 8, e1002739.
1025 Madhi, S.A., Cutland, C.L., Kuwanda, L., Weinberg, A., Hugo, A., Jones, S., Adrian, P.V., van
1026 Niekerk, N., Treurnicht, F., Ortiz, J.R., *et al.* (2014). Influenza vaccination of pregnant women
1027 and protection of their infants. *The New England journal of medicine* 371, 918-931.
1028 Madhi, S.A., Polack, F.P., Piedra, P.A., Munoz, F.M., Trenholme, A.A., Simoes, E.A.F., Swamy,
1029 G.K., Agrawal, S., Ahmed, K., August, A., *et al.* (2020). Respiratory Syncytial Virus Vaccination
1030 during Pregnancy and Effects in Infants. *The New England journal of medicine* 383, 426-439.
1031 Martinez, D.R., Fong, Y., Li, S.H., Yang, F., Jennewein, M.F., Weiner, J.A., Harrell, E.A.,
1032 Mangold, J.F., Goswami, R., Seage, G.R., 3rd, *et al.* (2019). Fc Characteristics Mediate
1033 Selective Placental Transfer of IgG in HIV-Infected Women. *Cell* 178, 190-201.e111.
1034 Martinez, D.R., Fouda, G.G., Peng, X., Ackerman, M.E., and Permar, S.R. (2018).
1035 Noncanonical placental Fc receptors: What is their role in modulating transplacental transfer of
1036 maternal IgG? *PLoS Pathog* 14, e1007161.
1037 Martinez, D.R., Tu, J.J., Kumar, A., Mangold, J.F., Mangan, R.J., Goswami, R., Giorgi, E.E.,
1038 Chen, J., Mengual, M., Douglas, A.O., *et al.* (2020). Maternal Broadly Neutralizing Antibodies
1039 Can Select for Neutralization-Resistant, Infant-Transmitted/Founder HIV Variants. *mBio* 11.
1040 Matsui, S.M., Offit, P.A., Vo, P.T., Mackow, E.R., Benfield, D.A., Shaw, R.D., Padilla-Noriega,
1041 L., and Greenberg, H.B. (1989). Passive protection against rotavirus-induced diarrhea by
1042 monoclonal antibodies to the heterotypic neutralization domain of VP7 and the VP8 fragment of
1043 VP4. *Journal of clinical microbiology* 27, 780-782.
1044 Mayer, C., VanHise, K., Caskey, R., Naqvi, M., and Burwick, R.M. (2021). Monoclonal
1045 Antibodies Casirivimab and Imdevimab in Pregnancy for Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-
1046 19). *Obstetrics and gynecology* 138, 937-939.
1047 Mazur, N.I., Horsley, N.M., Englund, J.A., Nederend, M., Magaret, A., Kumar, A., Jacobino,
1048 S.R., de Haan, C.A.M., Khatry, S.K., LeClerq, S.C., *et al.* (2019). Breast Milk Prefusion F
1049 Immunoglobulin G as a Correlate of Protection Against Respiratory Syncytial Virus Acute
1050 Respiratory Illness. *The Journal of infectious diseases* 219, 59-67.

1051 McLellan, J.S., Chen, M., Joyce, M.G., Sastry, M., Stewart-Jones, G.B., Yang, Y., Zhang, B.,
1052 Chen, L., Srivatsan, S., Zheng, A., *et al.* (2013). Structure-based design of a fusion glycoprotein
1053 vaccine for respiratory syncytial virus. *Science (New York, NY)* 342, 592-598.
1054 Megli, C.J., and Coyne, C.B. (2022). Infections at the maternal-fetal interface: an overview of
1055 pathogenesis and defence. *Nature reviews Microbiology* 20, 67-82.
1056 Mehta, P.D., Mehta, S.P., and Isaacs, C.E. (1989). Distribution of IgG subclasses in human
1057 colostrum and milk. *Immunology letters* 22, 235-238.
1058 Metz, T.D., Clifton, R.G., Hughes, B.L., Sandoval, G.J., Grobman, W.A., Saade, G.R., Manuck,
1059 T.A., Longo, M., Sowles, A., Clark, K., *et al.* (2022). Association of SARS-CoV-2 Infection With
1060 Serious Maternal Morbidity and Mortality From Obstetric Complications. *Jama*.
1061 Milligan, C., Richardson, B.A., John-Stewart, G., Nduati, R., and Overbaugh, J. (2015).
1062 Passively acquired antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC) activity in HIV-infected
1063 infants is associated with reduced mortality. *Cell host & microbe* 17, 500-506.
1064 Modjarrad, K., Lin, L., George, S.L., Stephenson, K.E., Eckels, K.H., De La Barrera, R.A.,
1065 Jarman, R.G., Sondergaard, E., Tennant, J., Ansel, J.L., *et al.* (2018). Preliminary aggregate
1066 safety and immunogenicity results from three trials of a purified inactivated Zika virus vaccine
1067 candidate: phase 1, randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trials. *Lancet (London,*
1068 *England)* 391, 563-571.
1069 Mold, J.E., Michaëlsson, J., Burt, T.D., Muench, M.O., Beckerman, K.P., Busch, M.P., Lee, T.H.,
1070 Nixon, D.F., and McCune, J.M. (2008). Maternal alloantigens promote the development of
1071 tolerogenic fetal regulatory T cells in utero. *Science (New York, NY)* 322, 1562-1565.
1072 Morteau, O., Gerard, C., Lu, B., Ghiran, S., Rits, M., Fujiwara, Y., Law, Y., Distelhorst, K.,
1073 Nielsen, E.M., Hill, E.D., *et al.* (2008). An indispensable role for the chemokine receptor CCR10
1074 in IgA antibody-secreting cell accumulation. *Journal of immunology (Baltimore, Md : 1950)* 181,
1075 6309-6315.
1076 Moylan, D.C., Pati, S.K., Ross, S.A., Fowler, K.B., Boppana, S.B., and Sabbaj, S. (2017). Breast
1077 Milk Human Cytomegalovirus (CMV) Viral Load and the Establishment of Breast Milk CMV-
1078 pp65-Specific CD8 T Cells in Human CMV Infected Mothers. *The Journal of infectious diseases*
1079 216, 1176-1179.
1080 Msallam, R., Balla, J., Rathore, A.P.S., Kared, H., Malleret, B., Saron, W.A.A., Liu, Z., Hang,
1081 J.W., Dutertre, C.A., Larbi, A., *et al.* (2020). Fetal mast cells mediate postnatal allergic
1082 responses dependent on maternal IgE. *Science (New York, NY)* 370, 941-950.
1083 Mutucumarana, C.P., Eudailey, J., McGuire, E.P., Vandergrift, N., Tegha, G., Chasela, C.,
1084 Ellington, S., van der Horst, C., Kourtis, A.P., Permar, S.R., *et al.* (2017). Maternal Humoral
1085 Immune Correlates of Peripartum Transmission of Clade C HIV-1 in the Setting of Peripartum
1086 Antiretrovirals. *Clin Vaccine Immunol* 24.
1087 Niewiesk, S. (2014). Maternal antibodies: clinical significance, mechanism of interference with
1088 immune responses, and possible vaccination strategies. *Frontiers in immunology* 5, 446.
1089 O'Brien, K.L., Chandran, A., Weatherholtz, R., Jafri, H.S., Griffin, M.P., Bellamy, T., Millar, E.V.,
1090 Jensen, K.M., Harris, B.S., Reid, R., *et al.* (2015). Efficacy of motavizumab for the prevention of
1091 respiratory syncytial virus disease in healthy Native American infants: a phase 3 randomised
1092 double-blind placebo-controlled trial. *The Lancet Infectious diseases* 15, 1398-1408.
1093 Offit, P.A., Shaw, R.D., and Greenberg, H.B. (1986). Passive protection against rotavirus-
1094 induced diarrhea by monoclonal antibodies to surface proteins vp3 and vp7. *J Virol* 58, 700-703.
1095 Ogra, S.S., Weintraub, D., and Ogra, P.L. (1977). Immunologic aspects of human colostrum and
1096 milk. III. Fate and absorption of cellular and soluble components in the gastrointestinal tract of
1097 the newborn. *Journal of immunology (Baltimore, Md : 1950)* 119, 245-248.
1098 Oguti, B., Ali, A., Andrews, N., Barug, D., Anh Dang, D., Halperin, S.A., Thu Hoang, H.T.,
1099 Holder, B., Kampmann, B., Kazi, A.M., *et al.* (2022). The half-life of maternal transplacental
1100 antibodies against diphtheria, tetanus, and pertussis in infants: an individual participant data
1101 meta-analysis. *Vaccine* 40, 450-458.

1102 Ohmit, S.E., Petrie, J.G., Cross, R.T., Johnson, E., and Monto, A.S. (2011). Influenza
1103 hemagglutination-inhibition antibody titer as a correlate of vaccine-induced protection. *The*
1104 *Journal of infectious diseases* 204, 1879-1885.

1105 Omer, S.B. (2017). Maternal Immunization. *The New England journal of medicine* 376, 1256-
1106 1267.

1107 Otero, C.E., Langel, S.N., Blasi, M., and Permar, S.R. (2020). Maternal antibody interference
1108 contributes to reduced rotavirus vaccine efficacy in developing countries. *PLoS Pathog* 16,
1109 e1009010.

1110 Pammi, M., Cope, J., Tarr, P.I., Warner, B.B., Morrow, A.L., Mai, V., Gregory, K.E., Kroll, J.S.,
1111 McMurtry, V., Ferris, M.J., *et al.* (2017). Intestinal dysbiosis in preterm infants preceding
1112 necrotizing enterocolitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Microbiome* 5, 31.

1113 Pass, R.F., Zhang, C., Evans, A., Simpson, T., Andrews, W., Huang, M.L., Corey, L., Hill, J.,
1114 Davis, E., Flanagan, C., *et al.* (2009). Vaccine prevention of maternal cytomegalovirus infection.
1115 *The New England journal of medicine* 360, 1191-1199.

1116 Pauthner, M.G., Nkolola, J.P., Havenar-Daughton, C., Murrell, B., Reiss, S.M., Bastidas, R.,
1117 Prevost, J., Nedellec, R., von Bredow, B., Abbink, P., *et al.* (2019). Vaccine-Induced Protection
1118 from Homologous Tier 2 SHIV Challenge in Nonhuman Primates Depends on Serum-
1119 Neutralizing Antibody Titers. *Immunity* 50, 241-252 e246.

1120 Peri, B.A., Theodore, C.M., Losonsky, G.A., Fishaut, J.M., Rothberg, R.M., and Ogra, P.L.
1121 (1982). Antibody content of rabbit milk and serum following inhalation or ingestion of respiratory
1122 syncytial virus and bovine serum albumin. *Clin Exp Immunol* 48, 91-101.

1123 Permar, S.R., Fong, Y., Vandergrift, N., Fouda, G.G., Gilbert, P., Parks, R., Jaeger, F.H.,
1124 Pollara, J., Martelli, A., Liebl, B.E., *et al.* (2015). Maternal HIV-1 envelope-specific antibody
1125 responses and reduced risk of perinatal transmission. *The Journal of clinical investigation* 125,
1126 2702-2706.

1127 Perrin, M.T., Fogleman, A.D., Newburg, D.S., and Allen, J.C. (2017). A longitudinal study of
1128 human milk composition in the second year postpartum: implications for human milk banking.
1129 *Maternal & child nutrition* 13.

1130 Perruzza, L., Jaconi, S., Lombardo, G., Pinna, D., Strati, F., Morone, D., Seehusen, F., Hu, Y.,
1131 Bajoria, S., Xiong, J., *et al.* (2020). Prophylactic Activity of Orally Administered FliD-Reactive
1132 Monoclonal IgA Against *Campylobacter* Infection. *Frontiers in immunology* 11, 1011.

1133 Planitzer, C.B., Saemann, M.D., Gajek, H., Farcet, M.R., and Kreil, T.R. (2011).
1134 Cytomegalovirus neutralization by hyperimmune and standard intravenous immunoglobulin
1135 preparations. *Transplantation* 92, 267-270.

1136 Pou, C., Nkulikiyimfura, D., Henckel, E., Olin, A., Lakshmikanth, T., Mikes, J., Wang, J., Chen,
1137 Y., Bernhardsson, A.K., Gustafsson, A., *et al.* (2019). The repertoire of maternal anti-viral
1138 antibodies in human newborns. *Nat Med* 25, 591-596.

1139 Price, J.F., Kemeny, D.M., Richards, D., and Richardson, V.F. (1987). IgG subclass antibody
1140 production to milk and egg antigens during infancy. *Pediatric Research* 22, 223-223.

1141 Ramanan, D., Sefik, E., Galván-Peña, S., Wu, M., Yang, L., Yang, Z., Kostic, A., Golovkina,
1142 T.V., Kasper, D.L., Mathis, D., *et al.* (2020). An Immunologic Mode of Multigenerational
1143 Transmission Governs a Gut Treg Setpoint. *Cell* 181, 1276-1290.e1213.

1144 Ramani, S., Stewart, C.J., Laucirica, D.R., Ajami, N.J., Robertson, B., Autran, C.A., Shinge, D.,
1145 Rani, S., Anandan, S., Hu, L., *et al.* (2018). Human milk oligosaccharides, milk microbiome and
1146 infant gut microbiome modulate neonatal rotavirus infection. *Nature communications* 9, 5010-
1147 5010.

1148 Rasmussen, S.A., Jamieson, D.J., Honein, M.A., and Petersen, L.R. (2016). Zika Virus and
1149 Birth Defects--Reviewing the Evidence for Causality. *The New England journal of medicine* 374,
1150 1981-1987.

1151 Rasmussen, S.A., Jamieson, D.J., and Uyeki, T.M. (2012). Effects of influenza on pregnant
1152 women and infants. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 207, S3-8.

1153 Revello, M.G., Lazzarotto, T., Guerra, B., Spinillo, A., Ferrazzi, E., Kustermann, A., Guaschino,
1154 S., Vergani, P., Todros, T., Frusca, T., *et al.* (2014). A randomized trial of hyperimmune globulin
1155 to prevent congenital cytomegalovirus. *The New England journal of medicine* 370, 1316-1326.
1156 Richards, A.F., Doering, J.E., Lozito, S.A., Varrone, J.J., Willsey, G.G., Pauly, M., Whaley, K.,
1157 Zeitlin, L., and Mantis, N.J. (2020). Inhibition of invasive salmonella by orally administered IgA
1158 and IgG monoclonal antibodies. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases* 14, e0007803.
1159 Richardson, S.I., Lambson, B.E., Crowley, A.R., Bashirova, A., Scheepers, C., Garrett, N.,
1160 Abdool Karim, S., Mkhize, N.N., Carrington, M., Ackerman, M.E., *et al.* (2019). IgG3 enhances
1161 neutralization potency and Fc effector function of an HIV V2-specific broadly neutralizing
1162 antibody. *PLoS Pathog* 15, e1008064.
1163 Ringe, R.P., Sanders, R.W., Yasmeen, A., Kim, H.J., Lee, J.H., Cupo, A., Korzun, J., Derking,
1164 R., van Montfort, T., Julien, J.P., *et al.* (2013). Cleavage strongly influences whether soluble
1165 HIV-1 envelope glycoprotein trimers adopt a native-like conformation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*
1166 110, 18256-18261.
1167 Robbiani, D.F., Olsen, P.C., Costa, F., Wang, Q., Oliveira, T.Y., Nery, N., Jr., Aromolaran, A.,
1168 do Rosario, M.S., Sacramento, G.A., Cruz, J.S., *et al.* (2019). Risk of Zika microcephaly
1169 correlates with features of maternal antibodies. *The Journal of experimental medicine* 216,
1170 2302-2315.
1171 Roux, M.E., McWilliams, M., Phillips-Quagliata, J.M., Weisz-Carrington, P., and Lamm, M.E.
1172 (1977). Origin of IgA-secreting plasma cells in the mammary gland. *The Journal of experimental*
1173 *medicine* 146, 1311-1322.
1174 Rozhnova, G., M, E.K., van der Klis, F., van Baarle, D., Korndewal, M., A, C.V., and van Boven,
1175 M. (2020). Short- and long-term impact of vaccination against cytomegalovirus: a modeling
1176 study. *BMC Med* 18, 174.
1177 Ruben, F.L., Holzman, I.R., and Fireman, P. (1982). Responses of lymphocytes from human
1178 colostrum or milk to influenza antigens. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 143, 518-
1179 522.
1180 Ruiz-Palacios, G.M., Cervantes, L.E., Ramos, P., Chavez-Munguia, B., and Newburg, D.S.
1181 (2003). *Campylobacter jejuni* binds intestinal H(O) antigen (Fuc alpha 1, 2Gal beta 1, 4GlcNAc),
1182 and fucosyloligosaccharides of human milk inhibit its binding and infection. *The Journal of*
1183 *biological chemistry* 278, 14112-14120.
1184 Russell, E.S., Kwiek, J.J., Keys, J., Barton, K., Mwapasa, V., Montefiori, D.C., Meshnick, S.R.,
1185 and Swanstrom, R. (2011). The genetic bottleneck in vertical transmission of subtype C HIV-1 is
1186 not driven by selection of especially neutralization-resistant virus from the maternal viral
1187 population. *J Virol* 85, 8253-8262.
1188 Russell, E.S., Ojeda, S., Fouda, G.G., Meshnick, S.R., Montefiori, D., Permar, S.R., and
1189 Swanstrom, R. (2013). Short communication: HIV type 1 subtype C variants transmitted through
1190 the bottleneck of breastfeeding are sensitive to new generation broadly neutralizing antibodies
1191 directed against quaternary and CD4-binding site epitopes. *AIDS research and human*
1192 *retroviruses* 29, 511-515.
1193 Sabbaj, S., Edwards, B.H., Ghosh, M.K., Semrau, K., Cheelo, S., Thea, D.M., Kuhn, L., Ritter,
1194 G.D., Mulligan, M.J., Goepfert, P.A., *et al.* (2002). Human immunodeficiency virus-specific
1195 CD8(+) T cells in human breast milk. *J Virol* 76, 7365-7373.
1196 Sabbaj, S., Ghosh, M.K., Edwards, B.H., Leeth, R., Decker, W.D., Goepfert, P.A., and
1197 Aldrovandi, G.M. (2005). Breast milk-derived antigen-specific CD8+ T cells: an extralymphoid
1198 effector memory cell population in humans. *J Immunol* 174, 2951-2956.
1199 Sacha, C.R., Vandergrift, N., Jeffries, T.L., Jr., McGuire, E., Fouda, G.G., Liebl, B., Marshall,
1200 D.J., Gurley, T.C., Stiegel, L., Whitesides, J.F., *et al.* (2015). Restricted isotype, distinct variable
1201 gene usage, and high rate of gp120 specificity of HIV-1 envelope-specific B cells in colostrum
1202 compared with those in blood of HIV-1-infected, lactating African women. *Mucosal immunology*
1203 8, 316-326.

1204 Sánchez-Salguero, E., Mondragón-Ramírez, G.K., Alcántara-Montiel, J.C., Cébulo-Vázquez,
1205 A., Villegas-Domínguez, X., Contreras-Vargas, V.M., Thompson-Bonilla, M.D.R., Romero-
1206 Ramírez, H., and Santos-Argumedo, L. (2019). Infectious episodes during pregnancy, at
1207 particular mucosal sites, increase specific IgA1 or IgA2 subtype levels in human colostrum.
1208 *Maternal health, neonatology and perinatology* 5, 9.

1209 Sanders, R.W., van Gils, M.J., Derking, R., Sok, D., Ketas, T.J., Burger, J.A., Ozorowski, G.,
1210 Cupo, A., Simonich, C., Goo, L., *et al.* (2015). HIV-1 VACCINES. HIV-1 neutralizing antibodies
1211 induced by native-like envelope trimers. *Science (New York, NY)* 349, aac4223.

1212 Sapparapu, G., Fernandez, E., Kose, N., Bin, C., Fox, J.M., Bombardi, R.G., Zhao, H., Nelson,
1213 C.A., Bryan, A.L., Barnes, T., *et al.* (2016). Neutralizing human antibodies prevent Zika virus
1214 replication and fetal disease in mice. *Nature* 540, 443-447.

1215 Schlaudecker, E.P., Ambroggio, L., McNeal, M.M., Finkelman, F.D., and Way, S.S. (2018).
1216 Declining responsiveness to influenza vaccination with progression of human pregnancy.
1217 *Vaccine* 36, 4734-4741.

1218 Schlaudecker, E.P., Steinhoff, M.C., Omer, S.B., McNeal, M.M., Roy, E., Arifeen, S.E., Dodd,
1219 C.N., Raqib, R., Breiman, R.F., and Zaman, K. (2013). IgA and neutralizing antibodies to
1220 influenza A virus in human milk: a randomized trial of antenatal influenza immunization. *PLoS*
1221 *One* 8, e70867.

1222 Schrotten, H., Hanisch, F.G., and Hansman, G.S. (2016). Human Norovirus Interactions with
1223 Histo-Blood Group Antigens and Human Milk Oligosaccharides. *J Virol* 90, 5855-5859.

1224 Semmes, E.C., and Coyne, C.B. (2021). Innate immune defenses at the maternal-fetal
1225 interface. *Current opinion in immunology* 74, 60-67.

1226 Semmes, E.C., Li, S.H., Hurst, J.H., Yang, Z., Niedzwiecki, D., Fouda, G.G., Kurtzberg, J.,
1227 Walsh, K.M., and Permar, S.R. (2021a). Congenital human cytomegalovirus infection is
1228 associated with decreased transplacental IgG transfer efficiency due to maternal
1229 hypergammaglobulinemia. *Clinical infectious diseases : an official publication of the Infectious*
1230 *Diseases Society of America*.

1231 Semmes, E.C., Miller, I.G., Jenks, J.A., Wimberly, C.E., Berendam, S.J., Harnois, M.J.,
1232 Webster, H., Hurst, J.H., Kurtzberg, J., Fouda, G.G., *et al.* (2021b). Maternal Fc-mediated non-
1233 neutralizing antibody responses correlate with protection against congenital human
1234 cytomegalovirus infection. 2021.2012.2005.21267312.

1235 Shan, C., Xie, X., Luo, H., Muruato, A.E., Liu, Y., Wakamiya, M., La, J.H., Chung, J.M., Weaver,
1236 S.C., Wang, T., *et al.* (2019). Maternal vaccination and protective immunity against Zika virus
1237 vertical transmission. *Nature communications* 10, 5677.

1238 Shi, T., McAllister, D.A., O'Brien, K.L., Simoes, E.A.F., Madhi, S.A., Gessner, B.D., Polack, F.P.,
1239 Balsells, E., Acacio, S., Aguayo, C., *et al.* (2017). Global, regional, and national disease burden
1240 estimates of acute lower respiratory infections due to respiratory syncytial virus in young
1241 children in 2015: a systematic review and modelling study. *Lancet (London, England)* 390, 946-
1242 958.

1243 Shingai, M., Nishimura, Y., Klein, F., Mouquet, H., Donau, O.K., Plishka, R., Buckler-White, A.,
1244 Seaman, M., Piatak, M., Jr., Lifson, J.D., *et al.* (2013). Antibody-mediated immunotherapy of
1245 macaques chronically infected with SHIV suppresses viraemia. *Nature* 503, 277-280.

1246 Shook, L.L., Atyeo, C.G., Yonker, L.M., Fasano, A., Gray, K.J., Alter, G., and Edlow, A.G.
1247 (2022). Durability of Anti-Spike Antibodies in Infants After Maternal COVID-19 Vaccination or
1248 Natural Infection. *Jama*.

1249 Shope, S.R., and Schiemann, D.A. (1991). Passive secretory immunity against *Salmonella*
1250 *typhimurium* demonstrated with foster mouse pups. *Journal of medical microbiology* 35, 53-59.

1251 Simister, N.E. (2003). Placental transport of immunoglobulin G. *Vaccine* 21, 3365-3369.

1252 Singh, T., Hwang, K.-K., Miller, A.S., Jones, R.L., Lopez, C.A., Giuberti, C., Gladden, M.A.,
1253 Miller, I., Webster, H.S., Eudailey, J.A., *et al.* (2021). Zika virus-specific IgM elicited during
1254 pregnancy exhibits ultrapotent neutralization. 2021.2011.2023.469700.

1255 Sitarik, A.R., Bobbitt, K.R., Havstad, S.L., Fujimura, K.E., Levin, A.M., Zoratti, E.M., Kim, H.,
1256 Woodcroft, K.J., Wegienka, G., Ownby, D.R., *et al.* (2017). Breast Milk Transforming Growth
1257 Factor β Is Associated With Neonatal Gut Microbial Composition. *Journal of pediatric*
1258 *gastroenterology and nutrition* 65, e60-e67.

1259 Sliepen, K., and Sanders, R.W. (2016). HIV-1 envelope glycoprotein immunogens to induce
1260 broadly neutralizing antibodies. *Expert Rev Vaccines* 15, 349-365.

1261 Stelzer, I.A., Urbschat, C., Schepanski, S., Thiele, K., Triviai, I., Wieczorek, A., Alawi, M.,
1262 Ohnezeit, D., Kottlau, J., Huang, J., *et al.* (2021). Vertically transferred maternal immune cells
1263 promote neonatal immunity against early life infections. *Nature communications* 12, 4706.

1264 Stensballe, L.G., Ravn, H., Kristensen, K., Agerskov, K., Meakins, T., Aaby, P., and Simões,
1265 E.A. (2009). Respiratory syncytial virus neutralizing antibodies in cord blood, respiratory
1266 syncytial virus hospitalization, and recurrent wheeze. *The Journal of allergy and clinical*
1267 *immunology* 123, 398-403.

1268 Stoppato, M., Gaspar, C., Regeimbal, J., Nunez, R.G., Giuntini, S., Schiller, Z.A., Gawron, M.A.,
1269 Pondish, J.R., Martin, J.C., 3rd, Schneider, M.I., *et al.* (2020). Oral administration of an anti-
1270 CfaE secretory IgA antibody protects against Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* diarrheal disease
1271 in a nonhuman primate model. *Vaccine* 38, 2333-2339.

1272 Sukumaran, L., McCarthy, N.L., Kharbanda, E.O., Weintraub, E.S., Vazquez-Benitez, G.,
1273 McNeil, M.M., Li, R., Klein, N.P., Hambidge, S.J., Naleway, A.L., *et al.* (2015). Safety of Tetanus
1274 Toxoid, Reduced Diphtheria Toxoid, and Acellular Pertussis and Influenza Vaccinations in
1275 Pregnancy. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 126, 1069-1074.

1276 Swanson, K.A., Settembre, E.C., Shaw, C.A., Dey, A.K., Rappuoli, R., Mandl, C.W., Dormitzer,
1277 P.R., and Carfi, A. (2011). Structural basis for immunization with postfusion respiratory syncytial
1278 virus fusion F glycoprotein (RSV F) to elicit high neutralizing antibody titers. *Proc Natl Acad Sci*
1279 *U S A* 108, 9619-9624.

1280 Sweet, C., Jakeman, K.J., and Smith, H. (1987). Role of milk-derived IgG in passive maternal
1281 protection of neonatal ferrets against influenza. *The Journal of general virology* 68 (Pt 10),
1282 2681-2686.

1283 Tabata, T., Petitt, M., Fang-Hoover, J., and Pereira, L. (2019). Survey of cellular immune
1284 responses to human cytomegalovirus infection in the microenvironment of the uterine-placental
1285 interface. *Med Microbiol Immunol* 208, 475-485.

1286 Taha, T.E. (2011). Mother-to-child transmission of HIV-1 in sub-Saharan Africa: past, present
1287 and future challenges. *Life sciences* 88, 917-921.

1288 Tapia, M.D., Sow, S.O., Tamboura, B., Tégueté, I., Pasetti, M.F., Kodio, M., Onwuchekwa, U.,
1289 Tennant, S.M., Blackwelder, W.C., Coulibaly, F., *et al.* (2016). Maternal immunisation with
1290 trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine for prevention of influenza in infants in Mali: a prospective,
1291 active-controlled, observer-blind, randomised phase 4 trial. *The Lancet Infectious diseases* 16,
1292 1026-1035.

1293 Thilagar, B.P., Ghosh, A.K., Nguyen, J., Theiler, R.N., Wick, M.J., Hurt, R.T., Razonable, R.R.,
1294 and Ganesh, R. (2022). Anti-Spike Monoclonal Antibody Therapy in Pregnant Women With
1295 Mild-to-Moderate Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Obstetrics and gynecology*.

1296 Thomas, A.S., Moreau, Y., Jiang, W., Isaac, J.E., Ewing, A., White, L.F., Kourtis, A.P., and
1297 Sagar, M. (2021). Pre-existing infant antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity associates with
1298 reduced HIV-1 acquisition and lower morbidity. *Cell reports Medicine* 2, 100412.

1299 Tokuhara, D., Álvarez, B., Mejima, M., Hiroiwa, T., Takahashi, Y., Kurokawa, S., Kuroda, M.,
1300 Oyama, M., Kozuka-Hata, H., Nochi, T., *et al.* (2013). Rice-based oral antibody fragment
1301 prophylaxis and therapy against rotavirus infection. *The Journal of clinical investigation* 123,
1302 3829-3838.

1303 Touzot, F., Dal-Cortivo, L., Verkarre, V., Lim, A., Crucis-Armengaud, A., Moshous, D., Héritier,
1304 S., Frange, P., Kaltenbach, S., Blanche, S., *et al.* (2012). Massive expansion of maternal T cells
1305 in response to EBV infection in a patient with SCID-XI. *Blood* 120, 1957-1959.

1306 Trégoat, V., Montagne, P., Béné, M.C., and Faure, G. (2001). Increases of IgA milk
1307 concentrations correlate with IgA2 increment. *Journal of clinical laboratory analysis* 15, 55-58.
1308 Tu, J.J., Kumar, A., Giorgi, E.E., Eudailey, J., LaBranche, C.C., Martinez, D.R., Fouda, G.G.,
1309 Moreau, Y., Thomas, A., Montefiori, D., *et al.* (2022). Vertical HIV-1 transmission in the setting
1310 of maternal broad and potent antibody responses. 2022.2002.2003.479075.
1311 Tuaille, E., Valea, D., Becquart, P., Al Tabaa, Y., Meda, N., Bollore, K., Van de Perre, P., and
1312 Vendrell, J.P. (2009). Human milk-derived B cells: a highly activated switched memory cell
1313 population primed to secrete antibodies. *Journal of immunology (Baltimore, Md : 1950)* 182,
1314 7155-7162.
1315 Tuboly, S., Bernáth, S., Glávits, R., Kovács, A., and Megyeri, Z. (1995). Intestinal absorption of
1316 colostrum lymphocytes in newborn lambs and their role in the development of immune status.
1317 *Acta veterinaria Hungarica* 43, 105-115.
1318 van Herwijnen, M.J.C., Driedonks, T.A.P., Snoek, B.L., Kroon, A.M.T., Kleinjan, M., Jorritsma,
1319 R., Pieterse, C.M.J., Hoen, E., and Wauben, M.H.M. (2018). Abundantly Present miRNAs in
1320 Milk-Derived Extracellular Vesicles Are Conserved Between Mammals. *Frontiers in nutrition* 5,
1321 81.
1322 Van Rompay, K.K.A., Coffey, L.L., Kapoor, T., Gazumyan, A., Keesler, R.I., Jurado, A., Peace,
1323 A., Agudelo, M., Watanabe, J., Usachenko, J., *et al.* (2020). A combination of two human
1324 monoclonal antibodies limits fetal damage by Zika virus in macaques. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*
1325 117, 7981-7989.
1326 Van Rompay, K.K.A., Keesler, R.I., Ardeshir, A., Watanabe, J., Usachenko, J., Singapuri, A.,
1327 Cruzen, C., Bliss-Moreau, E., Murphy, A.M., Yee, J.L., *et al.* (2019). DNA vaccination before
1328 conception protects Zika virus-exposed pregnant macaques against prolonged viremia and
1329 improves fetal outcomes. *Science translational medicine* 11.
1330 van Schooten, J., and van Gils, M.J. (2018). HIV-1 immunogens and strategies to drive antibody
1331 responses towards neutralization breadth. *Retrovirology* 15.
1332 Vono, M., Eberhardt, C.S., Auderset, F., Mastelic-Gavillet, B., Lemeille, S., Christensen, D.,
1333 Andersen, P., Lambert, P.H., and Siegrist, C.A. (2019). Maternal Antibodies Inhibit Neonatal
1334 and Infant Responses to Vaccination by Shaping the Early-Life B Cell Repertoire within
1335 Germinal Centers. *Cell reports* 28, 1773-1784.e1775.
1336 Vygen-Bonnet, S., Hellenbrand, W., Garbe, E., von Kries, R., Bogdan, C., Heininger, U., Röbl-
1337 Mathieu, M., and Harder, T. (2020). Safety and effectiveness of acellular pertussis vaccination
1338 during pregnancy: a systematic review. *BMC Infect Dis* 20, 136.
1339 Weichert, S., Koromyslova, A., Singh, B.K., Hansman, S., Jennewein, S., Schroten, H., and
1340 Hansman, G.S. (2016). Structural Basis for Norovirus Inhibition by Human Milk
1341 Oligosaccharides. *J Virol* 90, 4843-4848.
1342 Weisz-Carrington, P., Roux, M.E., McWilliams, M., Phillips-Quagliata, J.M., and Lamm, M.E.
1343 (1978). Hormonal induction of the secretory immune system in the mammary gland. *Proc Natl*
1344 *Acad Sci U S A* 75, 2928-2932.
1345 WHO (2020). Maternal and Neonatal Tetanus (MNT) elimination.
1346 Wilson, E., and Butcher, E.C. (2004). CCL28 controls immunoglobulin (Ig)A plasma cell
1347 accumulation in the lactating mammary gland and IgA antibody transfer to the neonate. *The*
1348 *Journal of experimental medicine* 200, 805-809.
1349 Wright, P.F., Lambert, J.S., Gorse, G.J., Hsieh, R.H., McElrath, M.J., Weinhold, K., Wara, D.W.,
1350 Anderson, E.L., Keefer, M.C., Jackson, S., *et al.* (1999). Immunization with envelope MN rgp120
1351 vaccine in human immunodeficiency virus-infected pregnant women. *The Journal of infectious*
1352 *diseases* 180, 1080-1088.
1353 Wu, X., Parast, A.B., Richardson, B.A., Nduati, R., John-Stewart, G., Mbori-Ngacha, D.,
1354 Rainwater, S.M., and Overbaugh, J. (2006). Neutralization escape variants of human
1355 immunodeficiency virus type 1 are transmitted from mother to infant. *J Virol* 80, 835-844.

1356 Zhang, H., Tully, D.C., Hoffmann, F.G., He, J., Kankasa, C., and Wood, C. (2010). Restricted
1357 genetic diversity of HIV-1 subtype C envelope glycoprotein from perinatally infected Zambian
1358 infants. *PLoS One* 5, e9294.
1359 Zhong, Z., Haltalli, M., Holder, B., Rice, T., Donaldson, B., O'Driscoll, M., Le-Doare, K.,
1360 Kampmann, B., and Tregoning, J.S. (2019). The impact of timing of maternal influenza
1361 immunization on infant antibody levels at birth. *Clin Exp Immunol* 195, 139-152.
1362 Zolla-Pazner, S., Cohen, S.S., Boyd, D., Kong, X.P., Seaman, M., Nussenzweig, M., Klein, F.,
1363 Overbaugh, J., and Totrov, M. (2016). Structure/Function Studies Involving the V3 Region of the
1364 HIV-1 Envelope Delineate Multiple Factors That Affect Neutralization Sensitivity. *J Virol* 90, 636-
1365 649.

1366

1367

1368

1369 **Figure 1 Transplacental transfer of maternal immunity**

1370 (A) Antibody characteristics that impact transplacental transfer

1371 (B) Mechanisms of antibody and maternal microchimeric cell transplacental transfer

1372 (C) Effector functions of maternal IgG antibodies including neutralization, antibody-

1373 dependent cellular phagocytosis (ADCP), antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity

1374 (ADCC), antibody-dependent complement deposition (ADCD). Mast cell activation is

1375 reported to be induced by maternal IgE.

1376 Created with BioRender.com

1377

1378

1379 **Figure 2 Human milk transfer of maternal immunity**

1380 (A) Immunomodulatory breast milk components

1381 (B) Receptor-mediated mechanisms of antibody passive transfer in the mammary gland

1382 (C) Immune regulation in the infant intestinal tract by breast milk components

1383 Created with BioRender.com

1384

1385

1386 **Figure 3 Therapeutic strategies for boosting pre- and postpartum maternal**
 1387 **antibodies for passive transfer through the placenta and milk during peripartum**
 1388 **period**

1389 Boosting maternal immunity pre- or postpartum by active vaccination or passive
 1390 administration of recombinant antibodies leads to increased transfer of maternal
 1391 antibodies to the fetus or neonate, respectively

1392 Created with BioRender.com